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² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D5.1

Audit of Management Recommendations 1

30/11/2019

Executive Summary

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles. The FarFish project is designed around six case study (SC) areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast- and southwest Atlantic.

The overarching objective of the FarFish project is to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters, both within the jurisdiction of non-EU nations as well as international waters. To achieve this, FarFish aims to develop practical, achievable and cost-effective fisheries management tools and advice. Among those tools are practical and user-friendly guidelines on how to create management recommendations (MRs) within these fisheries, based on the responsive fisheries management system (RFMS). The RFMS is an approach developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan⁴, which builds on the concepts of results-based management (RBM), where responsibility for fisheries management is to a point transferred to resource users, provided that they meet with necessary requirements set forth by the authorities.

The FarFish project is designed to go through two iterations in regard to the RFMS approach, where first version guidelines for making MRs are developed, they are then tested by applying them to the FarFish CSs and the MRs are then audited by an independent third party (D5.1 – this document). The audit is then used to improve the guidelines and ultimately the second version of the MRs.

This document contains the audit of the 1st MRs. The audit builds on the Audit Framework of the RFMS developed in EcoFishMan. The audit aims to create a basis for improving the guidelines for making MRs, the MR invitations and the MRs developed in the next iteration of the project, through a planned, independent, and documented evaluation to determine whether the MR is being implemented as agreed. The role of the auditor is to evaluate whether the contract between the authority and the operator has been fulfilled, in the sense that the OTs listed in the MR have been achieved. In this first audit, the MR for each CS is audited ex-ante, focusing on measuring the results of the MR, based on the indicators set for each of the OTs. Two tasks are performed by the auditor at this stage, to conform with the provided documentation system and if data is available, and conduct a sensitivity analysis to establish a baseline for the evaluation of the performance in the second version of the MR.

⁴ FP7 Project under grant agreement no. 265401

Across all CSs some common challenges are identified by the auditor, such as the lack of clear identification of the complete fleet participating in the respective fisheries, as well as a clear framework to involve local and non-EU fleets that states ways to enter the RFMS and to exit it as well. It is also suggested that a protocol for conflict resolution would strengthen the MRs. Almost all the MRs have defined OTs that aim to increase pressure to all fleets to strive for a “level playing-field” in the fisheries conducted by multiple fleets in international waters. Therefore, good practice recommendations in involving other fleets is fundamental to facilitate that advantages of the RFMS process are taken. This challenge can be tackled in a common manner, finding CS with shared characteristics such as Senegal and Mauritania black hake fisheries, Cape Verde and Seychelles tuna fisheries and/or the high seas CS.

Other common issues across CSs identified by the auditor is the lack of specificity in terms of timeline for monitoring and follow up of the management actions. Also, in terms of available resources i.e. human and financial resources, to operationalize the OTs, although these topics are mentioned, they are not considered specific enough or assigned to specific actions. The auditor suggests therefore to build the documents around the OTs and the indicators performance, to facilitate the audit of the performance of the MR in the second loop.

The first stage of the audit presents a good overview of the development of MRs in the six different FarFish CS, the RFMS process is running adequately, although timing for completion of tasks has been a challenge. The MR show that a great amount of work and dialogue has taken place, as well as that ambitious but achievable objectives have been set. Common challenges were found such the importance to describe stronger initiative to promote broader participation in the RFMS. Also, interesting opportunities were observed during the audit process, such as the possibility to use the capacity building programs to incentivise participation and adherence to the MRs.

All together the audit should provide a basis to improve and advance in the developed of the MRs in the next iteration of the FarFish project, enabling the operators to improve management goals and implementation strategies, tailoring management strategies to comply with policy requirements, while advancing their own objectives and making use of local knowledge and resources. Enabling responsive management with a clear documentation system and audit framework that allow for timely interventions and adaptive management (Nielsen et al., 2018).

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Abbreviations

ADAPI	Association of Portuguese Industrial Fishing-boat Owners, Portugal
AIS	Automatic Identification System
AMP	Maritime and Port Agency, Cape Verde
ANFACO-CECOPECA	National Association of Fish and Seafood Canning Manufactures (Representing EU fishing and processing sector)
CAFS	Chinese Academy of Fishery Sciences, governmental scientific institution of Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (MoA). The institution plays an influential role in Chinese national fisheries science and management policy.
CECAF	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries
CECAF-SC	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries Scientific Committee
CPUE	Catch per Unit Effort
CS	Case Study
DARE	Directory of Fisheries Management in Mauritania
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, EC
DGRM	General Directorate for Marine Resources, National Fisheries Authority, Cape Verde
DNEM	Directorate National of Maritime Economy, Cape Verde
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMS	Electronic monitoring system
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
FAD	Fish aggregating device
FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
HCR	Harvesting Control Rule
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
ICES	International Exploration of the Sea
IEO	Instituto Español De Oceanografía
IMR	Institute of Marine Research
IOTC	The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing
LDAC	Long Distance Advisory council, EU fisheries body representing stakeholders of both fishing sector and other groups of interest
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MFMP	National Fisheries Management Plan
MPFM	Department of Fisheries and Maritime Economy, Mauritania
MPFM	Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy, Senegal
MSY	Maximum sustainable Yield
OPAGAC	Organisation of associated producers of large tuna freezer vessels, representing the purse seine fleet
OPROMAR	Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín, Spain
ORTHONGEL	French organisation of producers of frozen and deep-frozen tropical tuna
OT	Outcome Target
RBM	Results Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organization
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System

SEA	South East Atlantic
SEAFO	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation
SFA	Seychelles fishing Authority
SFPA	EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements
SMSP	Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning
SWA	South-West Atlantic
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System

Key concepts and definitions

Authority	Organizational entity enacting authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission.
Auditor(s)	The auditor is an organization with a competence in evaluating the extent to which specific and measurable policy objectives, as pursued within management plans developed and implemented by operators, are met.
Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it. Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Recommendation (MR)	The management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery.
MR1 & MR2	FarFish is organised to go through two loops within the RFMS process. First version Management Recommendations are called MR1 and second version MR2.
Operator	Organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management plans and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority
OT	Outcome target (OT) is a specific and measurable performance goals defined for a fishery on the basis of agreed and appropriately authorized general goals, standards and principles, as defined by the authorities based on the policy objectives. OT can be a textual or mathematical statement that can be evaluated as "true" or "false", where "true" is the target value. Textual OT: A natural language statement that can be evaluated as "true" or "false", e.g. "stock assessment exists", "CAP has been developed" or "stakeholders have been consulted". Mathematical OT: Normally an inequality, where one of the terms is an indicator and the other one is a reference point or value. E.g. Catch \leq MSY, catch \leq MEY or emissions \leq limit (political reference point). The actual "true" or "false" value of the OT in question needs to be evaluated at specific times (e.g. once a year), e.g. based on the indicator and reference point value at that specific time.
RFMS	RFMS is a fisheries management approach developed within the EcoFishMan project. The RFMS is an adaptive management system that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management.

1 Introduction

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles. The FarFish project is designed around six case study (SC) areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast and southwest Atlantic.

The overarching objective of the FarFish project is to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters, both within the jurisdiction of non-EU nations as well as international waters. To achieve this, FarFish aims to develop practical, achievable and cost-effective fisheries management tools and advice which can be applied immediately. Among those tools are practical, applicable and user-friendly guidelines on how to create management recommendations (MRs) within these fisheries, based on the responsive fisheries management system (RFMS). The RFMS is an approach developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan⁵, which builds on the concepts of results-based management (RBM), where responsibility for fisheries management is to a point transferred to resource users, provided that they meet with necessary requirements set forth by the competent authorities and document that they can achieve specified management objectives.

The FarFish project is designed to go through two iterations in regard to the RFMS approach, where first version general guidelines for making MRs are developed (D3.1), they are then tested by applying them to the six FarFish CSs (D4.3) and the MRs are then audited by an independent third party (D5.1 – this document). The audit is then used to improve the guidelines and ultimately the second version of the MRs.

This document contains the audit of the 1st MRs for the six case studies in the FarFish project. The audit builds on the Audit Framework of the RFMS developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan. The audit aims to create a basis for improving the general guidelines for making MRs, the MR invitations and the MRs developed in the next iteration of the project, through a planned, independent, and documented evaluation to determine whether the MR –including the monitoring and the documentation measures – is being implemented as agreed.

⁵ FP7 Project under grant agreement no. 265401

In accordance with the general guidelines for making MRs (D3.1) there are several stages that needed to be completed for the MR1 to be audited. The process to develop these documents began with dialogues between the authority and operator(s) to facilitate a shared understanding of goals and expectations. The authority then extended an invitation to the operator(s) to develop the MRs, which were to include specifications of measurable objectives called Outcome Targets (OTs) to operationalize the goals of the MRs. OTs should only be defined in terms of indicators that operators are expected to be able to control enough throughout the relevant management actions. The OTs should define the area of responsibility for operators, beyond the OTs, the responsibility to achieve policy goals remains with the authority (Nielsen et al., 2018). Finally, the auditor acting as an independent agent with capacity to audit the MRs performance, is to review the documentation, and evaluate the extent to which the OTs have been achieved. The auditor then submits the audit to the authority and operator(s). The RFMS therefore conceptualizes RBM as a contract between an “authority” and one or more “operators” and, in practice, this contract is the MR.

The role of the auditor is to evaluate whether the contract between the authority and the operator has been fulfilled in the sense that the OTs listed in the MR have been achieved. In this first task, the MR for each FarFish CS is audited ex-ante, focusing on measuring the results of the MR, based on the indicators set for each of the OTs. Two tasks are performed by the auditor at this stage, to conform with the provided documentation system and if data is available, conduct a sensitivity analysis to establish a baseline for the evaluation of the performance in the second version of the MR.

2 Audit Framework

The audit for the first version of the MRs developed for each of the FarFish CSs builds on the Audit Framework of RFMS developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (EcoFishMan, 2012). The audit aims to creating a basis for improving the general guidelines for making MRs, the MR invitations and the MRs developed in the next iteration, through a planned, independent, and documented evaluation to determine whether the MR –including the monitoring and the documentation measures – is being implemented as agreed.

The role of the auditor is to evaluate whether the contract between the authority and the operator has been fulfilled in the sense that the OTs listed in the MRs have been achieved. In this first task, the MR for each CS will be audited ex-ante, focusing on measuring the results of the MR based on the indicators set for each of the OTs. Two tasks are performed by the auditor at this first stage, to conform with the provided documentation system and if data is available, conduct a sensitivity Audit to establish a baseline for the evaluation of the MR's performance in the second version of the MR.

The MR development process in RFMS includes three main stages, starting by the authority's invitation for developing a MR, followed by the operator's development of a MR proposal, and the authority's 'quality check' of this proposal and the RFMS planning process overall. The role of the Auditor, operators and auditor is described in Table 1, introducing an overview of main RFMS processes involving development, approval, implementation, audit and adaptation of a MR (FarFish, 2019a):

Table 1: Role of the authority, Operators and Auditor in the MR development

RFMS process: Agency/roles:	MR Invitation	MR development and approval	MR implementation	MR audit and adaptation
Authority	Arranges 'pre-invitation' meetings; Writes MRO and MR invitation	- Oversees RFMS process; - Quality checks MR proposal; - Requests revisions/ approves/rejects MR; - Potentially arranges public hearing on MR	May provide MR services (e.g. research and enforcement) if this is agreed in the MR	Revises OTs and requests MR revisions (if needed)
Operator	Dialogues with authority; participates in pre-invitation meeting	Develops, revises and submits MR proposal	Formally responsible for: - Implementing MR - Collecting data for MR audit	Adapts MR (if requested)
Auditor			Receives and analyses data from operators	Periodically audits MR performance regarding OTs. May suggest conditions to be met by operators.

The audit framework of MR evaluation has been structured as follows:

1.1. Audit on the implementation of MRs:

The procedures and processes for the data collection are analysed and it is identified the baseline for the socioeconomic evaluations. This stage is organized as follows:

- a) Documentation system conformance
- b) Sensitivity analysis

1.2. Audit on the performance of MRs:

It determines the actual accuracy of the OTs, assessing the effectiveness, compliance and the effects of the management plan. This stage is broken down into three phases:

- a) Effectiveness performance informs about the performance of the MR.
- b) Compliance analyses the quality of the reported information.
- c) MR effects evaluates the impact of the MR in socioeconomic terms.

As stated in the Audit Framework for RFMS⁶ “the auditor assesses whether or not (or the extent to which) the OTs are achieved. Further, the auditor provides updated information about implemented management actions and their apparent consequences⁷. For the operator, the assessment will provide a basis for drafting modified MR in FarFish. For the authority, the assessment may be a basis for implementing sanctions or set conditions (if OTs were not achieved), for rewarding achievements, or for revising OTs”. Therefore, with the available information this document includes an analysis of the documentation system conformance and effectiveness performance. In addition, the auditor can estimate the socio-economic effect of the MR by using simulated data for sensitivity and cost benefit analysis. However, this estimation is limited to the extent the case study simulations provide useful data for the intended analysis.

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address the main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized, and the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MR relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”⁸. According to the information available, the auditor considers that the risks have not been properly detailed in the MR. However, the MR establishes mechanisms to be adaptive and facilitate the implementation of the RFMS through this MR.

2.1 Audit on the implementation of Management Recommendations

The Audit Framework seeks to achieve an effective and precise assemble of reliable information applying adaptive management principles. In order to develop this task successfully, an audit of the management plan will be carried as soon as they are implemented. This stage is broken down in two phases:

2.1.1 Documentation System Conformance

The RFMS and particularly the MRs includes the documentation system that has been designed for measuring the performance on relevant indicators (EcoFishMan, 2013b), so that appropriate management responses may be triggered accurately. In this context, the auditor evaluates the conformance of the documentation system and the sensitivity analysis, combining a quantitative and qualitative analysis.

⁶. EcoFishMan Deliverable 4.4, p.8 (EcoFishMan, 2013b)

⁷ In practice, the effects of management actions may not be directly observed, as this will depend on the type of management measures used as well as the type and quality of the collected information.

⁸. Deliverable 4.4. p. 28 (EcoFishMan, 2013b)

In general, the Audit of the RFMS’ MR is a planned, independent, and documented evaluation to determine whether the MR – including the monitoring and the documentation measures – is being implemented as agreed. The documentation system conformance builds on ensuring accurate information, detailing the minimum criteria for reliable data and considering the cost-efficiency of the control system. This phase is organized in three subsequent steps explained⁹ in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1: Steps for auditing Document System Conformance

There are clear constraints and boundaries (organisational, financial, expertise, experience, etc.) that can only be resolved gradually over time. Therefore, the RFMS proposes to identify areas of responsibility, linked to transitional and stepwise implementation is sound. Areas of responsibility: the responsibility for the RFMS functions such as data collection, monitoring and control can be divided differently between operators, the authority or external contracted agencies. The operator may choose to leave specific functions (e.g. data collection or control) to be carried out by e.g. the authority in the way different functions should be made clear in the MR.

The assessment of the documentation system describes the detected evidence for each criterion, providing recommendations to the Authority and Operators to maintain or improve the information flow (if applicable).

⁹ Review Audit Framework for further explanations.

Additionally, considering the core role of the documentation system for the result-based management, a **risk analysis**¹⁰ will be carried out for those cases where evidences are not met. This analysis is built on the International Organization for Standardization (ISO)¹¹ norms that describe the identification of the sources of risks, the analysis of their consequences and the evaluation of management options as the base on risk assessment techniques (Cormier et al., 2013). Thus, the risk analysis of the documentation system will be organized as follows:

1. **Identification:** the reasons behind the lack of compliance of any quality criteria should be described and analysed. The output is summarized in a *risk profile*¹² associated to unaccomplished issues and the sources of them.

2. **Estimation:** the risks, identified in the previous step, are classified as follows:
 - i. **Low:** problems with the statistical design, spatial extent, temporal duration, non-specific content or the format of reports, i.e. appropriate form for each type of user (decision maker, fishing association, etc).

 - ii. **Medium:** the medium risks are classified as the three following points:
 1. *Incoherence* between MR data collection instruments and external regulations¹³, taking into account:
 - a. Redundancies due to the aggregation and harmonisation of data.
 - b. Overlapping in the required information among data collect instruments.
 - c. Inconsistencies to identify the responsibility for gathering data

 2. Data *relevance* and *availability*. Feasibility of the indicator's data requirements.

 3. *Confidentiality*¹⁴ linked with the use of data by control agencies and management authorities.

 - iii. **High:** any issue that does not allow obtaining evidence is defined as a high risk.

¹⁰ Risk analysis means the systematic identification of risks and the implementation of all measures necessary for limiting the occurrence of these risks. This includes activities such as collecting data and information, analysing and assessing risk, preparing and taking action, and regular monitoring and review of the process and its outcomes, based on the approved MR.

¹¹ In the framework of the ISO 31000:2009, Risk management – Principles and guidelines, provides principles, framework and a process for managing risk (International Organization for Standardization, 2009).

¹² Risk is defined as the likelihood of an event that may occur and would constitute a violation of the rules of the approved MR.

¹³ External regulations refer to requirements for data collection from national, European or International regulations on fisheries, environment, etc.

¹⁴ Data collected and exchanged in the framework of this Regulation should be treated in accordance with applicable rules on confidentiality. Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

3. **Recommendations:** a specific course of recommendations is suggested in Table 2, according to the identified and evaluated risks levels:

Table 2: Advice to Risk Level

Level of risk	Advise
Low	Continue with minor changes on drivers and pressures that cause the risk
Medium	Revision of the monitoring and documentation procedures ¹⁵ and processes ¹⁶ .
High	Redefinition of the OT, management strategies or indicators

In some cases, the risk analysis assumptions and methods, described in this audit framework, would also need a review to ensure the success of remedial actions. These ones could be linked to recent knowledge, new management strategies or technologies, new drivers or existing drivers are generating new pressures not anticipated, changes in the legislative and regulatory instruments or governance mandates or modifications in public policies that affect the management outcomes (Cormier et al., 2013). Finally, it should be combined in the iterative revision of indicators and strategies, learning and adapting the ongoing MR and determining if there is a need to trigger or redefine the management means.

On the other hand, the results from the Conformance assessment would be pictured following the “Lights Traffic” method (Caddy, 2002), which represents the documentation system conformity:

- No evidences (in any criteria) or a low level of risk: it would be pictured in **green**
- A medium level of risk: it would be pictured in **yellow**.
- A high level of risk: it would be pictured in **red**.

The process and steps to conduct the documentations system conformance is depicted in Figure 2.

¹⁵ Defined as practice or step.

¹⁶ Defined as series of actions.

Figure 2 Documentation system conformance (EcoFishMan, 2013a)

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of adherence to the OTs and are classified in three dimensions: Ecological, Socio-Economic and Governance. The indicators are classified according to their level of quality achieved from the most detailed measuring achievement in percentage (type A), followed by a moderate type of evaluation where the level of achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2) and low level (score 1) and not present (NL) (score 0). The last type of indicator measurability is type C, reflecting a measurement of indicators related to OT that can only have two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

This classification of indicators must also be dependent on what OT dimension the indicators is related to. This classification might work well for Governance indicators, but not or ecological and socioeconomics, where the metric could be more specific, e.g. by a D classification: actual measurement.

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2.1.2 Sensitivity analysis

The audit of the MRs implementation does also include **sensitivity analysis**. These are used to test whether changes in the selected key parameters lead to significant changes with regards to achieving the OTs for the MR. However, in order to conduct a sensitivity analysis, a baseline scenario must be established.

The baseline scenario depends on whether there are already are an MR in place or not:

- **NO MR:** if there is no MR, the baseline means the continuation of 'NO MR'. The 'NO MR' includes the expected effects of legislation which has been adopted but not yet implemented.
- **NO CHANGE MR:** where there is already an MR, the baseline is the continuation of the current policy without any change, i.e. without any new or additional EU intervention
- **CHANGE MR:** if the existing MR foresees a change, then the baseline can over time lead to a 'no EU policy' scenario. For practical reasons, you may use the existing policy without the 'sunset' as the baseline, provided you have an option only reflecting the introduction of the sunset clause.

A good baseline needs a strong factual basis and be expressed in quantitative terms. It needs an appropriate time horizon (neither too long nor too short). The baseline projection shall provide a clear indication of how serious the problem is, or to what extent it will become more serious without immediate intervention, and whether there are irreversible consequences.

The baseline scenario will take into account the expected results of relevant legislation which has been adopted but not yet fully implemented. While the baseline should not include developments that depend on political decisions that have not yet been taken, there is one important exception to this: if

the initiative is linked to other policy proposals already put forward by the Commission but not yet adopted by the legislator, these proposals need to be assumed to be part of the baseline.

The summary of the analysis of the fishery-dependent data is presented by using 25 socio-economic indicators following the procedure proposed by Accadia and Spagnolo (2006), and empirically developed by Ceriola et al. (2008). The economic indicators comprised seven indicators on economic performance, eight on productivity and four related to the market (costs and prices). The socio-economic indicators used by Ceriola et al. (2008) are presented below in Appendix 1.

In describing the baseline scenario – as when assessing the impacts of any policy option – we face the challenge that the projections are uncertain or that there is a risk attached to them, i.e. that an undesired development may – or may not – happen. Sensitivity analysis is a tool to respond to these challenges in baseline scenario.

Key parameters for the sensitivity analysis

The assumptions underlying the baseline scenario will vary as a result of external factors. Therefore, we conduct a sensitivity analysis to assess whether the effects of the MR differ significantly for different values of the key parameters.

Sensitivity analysis can be used to explore how the effects of the MR would change in response to variations in key parameters and how they interact¹⁷. The effects of the MR may be affected, for example, by changes in the total catch landed (x %) or the price of fish landed (y %) of fisheries who adopt a voluntary standard. While these values are rarely known for sure, there is often a range of values that is more or less likely. Sensitivity analysis can be used to establish how variations in such parameters affect the impact of the MR. A useful form of sensitivity analysis is to identify switching points. In other words, by how much does the value of an uncertain factor or a key assumption have to change in order for the preferred option to change. In that case we need to determine how likely it is that that critical value could be reached.

The key parameters selected for the sensitivity analysis are:

- Average days at sea
- Fishing effort (number of GT)
- Price trend (€/kg)
- Landed Catch (t)

¹⁷ For more on this see the JRC: <http://sensitivity-analysis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

The sensitivity of these key parameters will range from +50% to -50% compared the baseline scenario.

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a conceptual framework for the evaluation of the social desirability of a policy or project in order to facilitate a more efficient allocation of resources. Sensitivity analysis, which is an important component of CBA, involves changing parameters and recalculating the net present value of the project in order to identify the underlying uncertainty and convey how sensitive predicted impacts are to changes in assumptions.

The sensitivity analysis is thus not undertaken until the CBA has been completed, and the socio-economic effects of the new MR have become clear. This entails that it must be possible to carry out some form of CBA. As pointed out in Description of Action in FarFish, it was hoped that it would be possible to utilise available environmental, economic and social data to undertake a partial cost benefit analysis (PCBA) and/or cost efficiency analysis (CEA) for Case studies. Once those explorations had been completed, a thorough examination could be conducted on how changes in key variables could affect the ability of the MR in question to reach the desired OTs, and the socio-economic effects of these changes. In general, a successful monitoring and documentation system depends directly on developing efficient sampling programs that allow a cost-effective determination of the state of the resources, the socioeconomic situation and the effectiveness of strategies and management actions (Levin, Fogarty, Murawski, & Fluharty, 2009)

2.2 Audit on the Performance of Management Recommendations

The RFMS proposes to audit the MR performance periodically. This second stage is a platform for the responsiveness, i.e. it provides useful information about several key management points that allows to trigger management actions. The phases to support this stage are systematized as follows:

2.2.1 Effectiveness Performance

The Auditor should receive evidence about achievement (or not) of the OTs and finally, demonstrate the success or failure to perform the management goals. In this sense, the effectiveness performance is focused on measuring the results of the MR based on indicators, which should be classified as biological, ecological, economic, social and cultural according to the Management Plan Guidelines of the RFMS. This phase is organized in three subsequent steps as shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Steps to audit Effectiveness Performance

2.2.2 Compliance

In this compliance phase the auditor develops a quality and quantity analysis on the reported information in terms of completeness, time-related and sources. This analysis is done in three steps described in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Steps to audit Compliance

As a result, a summary effectiveness ratio will inform both Authority and Operators about the compliance's state of the reported data (including gaps, limitations, etc.). The results from the effectiveness analysis are shown using the traffic light method (Caddy, 2002), which provides thresholds (yellow lights) which represent an "early warning" to reduce the probability that a target or reference limit point would be exceeded (Hall & Mainprize, 2004). This guarantees a high probability of keeping compliance.

2.2.3 Management Recommendations Effects

In this third and final phase, the auditor will conduct an evaluation based on the sensitivity analysis, to conclude on the potential effects of the MR on the evaluated fishery, as well as in the correspondent society. In this step, the cost benefit analysis (CBA) provides a consistent methodology for project and policy appraisal (Angelsen & Sumaila, 1995). The elements of objective measurements should be sought at all reality levels, including hard facts (which cover natural science), artefacts (social science) and institutional facts (legal science).

The “audit dashboard” summarizes the audit results of the MR implementation. It aims to serve as an operational tool which provides feedback to both Authority and Operator. An illustration of the “Audit dashboard” can be seen in Figure 5 based on results from the project EcoFishMan (2014).

	PHASE	Rating	MP2 _{Case 3}	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3
STEP 1: MP IMPLEMEN- -TATION	Documentation system	Risk level	OT 1 – OT 5			N/A
	Documentation system	Risk level	OT 6 – OT 8			
	Documentation system	Risk level	OT 9			N/A
	Documentation system	Risk level	OT 10			N/A
	Documentation system	Risk level	OT 11 – OT 14			N/A
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline	Lack data for PCBA			
		Alternative MP	Lack data for PCBA			
Optimistic scenario		Lack data for PCBA				
Pessimistic scenario		Lack data for PCBA				
Responsive Assessment			OT	10763	13762	13888
STEP 2: PERFOR- -MANCE EVALU- -ATION	Performance Assessment		1			
	Performance Assessment		2			
	Performance Assessment		3			
	Performance Assessment		4			
	Performance Assessment		5			
	Performance Assessment		9			
	Performance Assessment		11			
	Compliance Assessment	Due to theoretical approach		N/A	N/A	N/A
	MP Effects	Lack of data		N/A	N/A	N/A
Responsive assessment			On-going & ex-post	On-going & ex-post	On-going & ex-post	On-going & ex-post
FINALASSESSMENT OF RFMS			EMP+CBA	EMP+CBA	EMP+CBA	EMP+CBA

Figure 5: Audit Dashboard with a summary of the evaluation of the MR

3 Audit Implementation Management Recommendations 1 for all Case Studies

3.1 Case Study 1: South-West Atlantic

3.1.1 Documentation System Conformance

This management recommendation (MR1^{*}) was proposed for the international mixed fishery in FAO Area 41, in the subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2, at the part of the Patagonian shelf and slope (< 300m) that extends beyond the Argentina EEZ and the Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone. This area does not have a Regional Fisheries Organization Organisations acting as key body responsible for managing fisheries, which makes the coexistence of international fleets within the area difficult, especially due to the different levels of compliance and enforcement of the flag states.

The MR1 should follow the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019a) and is based on the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2019b), where the outcome targets (OTs) were proposed. As the MR has been delivered to the auditor, this means the document has been approved by the authority, therefore the Auditor assumes that the following questions in Table 3, as defined in the checklist for the operators in the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019a), have been reviewed by the Authority. The table shows a summary of the Auditor's review for each item on the checklist i.e. whether each item is considered adequately addressed, partly addressed or not sufficiently addressed.

* 1st version MR

Table 3: Authority Checklist for MR1 for SWA

1.	Have you proposed a management strategy and identified measures that make it clear how you intend to achieve the obligatory OTs mentioned in section 3 of the MR guideline?	Yes
2	Have you identified risks and uncertainties regarding the above-mentioned strategy, and have you explained how it may be adapted?	Yes
3	Have you explained how it will be ensured that individual participants will comply with the measures identified in the plan?	No
4	Do you have a strategy for monitoring fisheries activities?	No
5	In case that it is found that some participants do not comply with agreed measures, have you identified sanctions that reflect the severity of likely or foreseeable offences?	Yes
6	Have you described how information will be collected that allows for an audit of whether or not the OTs are achieved? It is clear who will collect each type of data, and is it clear when they should do this?	No
7	Have you agreed with the authority on who will serve as auditor, and how its service will be paid?	Yes
8	Is it clear how responsibility will be divided between “authority”, “operators” and “auditor”? Is it clear when each agency should carry out each of their tasks, and is it clear who should cover the costs of this?	Partially
9	Have you explained how the members of your organization(s) have been informed and involved in decision-making regarding the MR development?	Partially
10	Is it clear how adequate communication between the agencies (“assessors”, “authorities” and “operators”) is ensured?	Yes

According to the auditor, points 3, 4 and 6 are not addressed and points 8 and 9 are partially covered in the MR1 for SWA. These points will be elaborated throughout the audit process.

Within the RFMS process, there are three main entities that have specific roles and responsibilities, namely the authorities, operators and auditors. MR1 for SWA describes the roles of these entities as required in the General Guidelines (FarFish, D3.1). The auditor will review the clarity and specificity in describing the authority and operators for SWA:

AUTHORITIES

Due to the absence of a Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO) in SWA international waters of the Patagonian shelf, there is no competent fisheries management authority in this area to take the lead in the RFMS process. Following, FarFish Work Package 3 representatives will act as the leading authority, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. FAO, DG MARE and CAFS. It is not clear who from WP3 represent as authority in SWA, Matis or NOFIMA and the main contact person in the process is not mentioned.

OPERATOR

The European fleet take part in the mixed-fisheries in SWA (FAO Area 41 and other important DWF from non-European fleets fishing in ABNJ come from China, Taiwan and Korea (FarFish, 2019c). The main fishing areas are at the part of Patagonian shelf and southern slope between 110 and 250 m depth, extending beyond the Argentinian EEZ and the Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone (FOCZ). The EU fleet operating in this area is almost exclusively represented by Spanish trawlers over 40 m and is the most important DWF in the area. The Spanish fleet consists of up to 19 vessels, ranging from 696 to 1,819 GT, with an average of about 1,190 GT. The Spanish long-distance freezer trawler fleet and long liners are based in Galician ports, mainly in Vigo.

The target species are mainly represented by Argentine Hake (*Merluccius hubbsi*), Argentine shortfin squid (*Illex argentinus*), Patagonian squid (*Loligo gahi*), Antarctic rockcod (Nototheniidae), Longtail southern cod (*Patagonotothen ramsayi*) and southern blue whiting (*Micromesistius australis*). The main by-catch species in this fishery is Patagonian grenadier (*Macruronus magellanicus*) and Patagonian toothfish (*Dissostichus eleginoides*), but also Rays mantas nei (*Rajiformes*), Stingrays (*Dasyatis spp.*), Longtail southern cod (*Patagonotothen ramsayi*) and Forkbeard (*Phycis phycis*) occurs. Argentine hake is the main target species for demersal trawl, but also Patagonian grenadier, Patagonian squid, cod, croaker and blue whiting are caught by bottom trawl. Other important gears applied in the area are longline and purse seiners.

MR1 set the European operators qualified to respond to the MR Invitation and will provide feedback through the Distance Advisory Council (LDAC). LDAC developed this MR draft aided by CETMAR and FarFish Work Package 4 lead by UiT, aiming to demonstrate how to meet the OTs listed in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018d). The OTs have been revised during this process, illustrating the iterative dialogue between authority and operators that characterizes the RFMS.

Due to the voluntary role of participating in the RFMS, it is not clear what vessels will be finally involved. A list with the implicated vessels is recommended to be presented at the beginning of the MR, which could be updated at the end of the year, if necessary.

From the MR description it is not clear to what extent all vessels of the same fishing organisation will accept and participate in the MR. Is the assumption that if a fishing association agrees to join in a RFMS' MR, all their members (vessels or skippers) accept the MR?

If not, then each vessel/skipper can choose to be managed under RFMS or not. This fact could cause:

- Increase of management and monitoring cost for operator as well for Authority.
- Lack of trust in the system due to the absence of same level playing field.
- The impact of the MR and its contributions to the overall management objectives would be reduced.

Following with the audit framework, the auditor proceeds to analyse the documentation in the different sections of the MR1.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION

The main goal of the MR for SWA are to improve the sustainability of high seas mixed fisheries at Patagonian shelf by (1) the inclusion of soft-law mechanisms, (2) improve the quality and quantity of data collection, (3) contribute to improved fishing and conservation through monitoring, control and surveillance mechanisms and thereby (4) contribute to a level playing field for international fleets involved.

The reasons or background for these main goals are not expressed exclusively. The background of the main goals should be addressed directly link to the challenges in fisheries of SWA.

There is inconsistency in describing OT 1.3, whether aims to set a pilot project on operational coordination or to develop a theoretical frame as basis for future pilot project.

MR PLANNING PERIOD

The active participation of operators allows FarFish to have a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021).

INCENTIVES and SANCTIONS

In general, the MR1 lack descriptions of incentives and sanctions in relation to the OTs, due to the limited control over the resource by operators and due to lack of a RFMO in SWA. It is acknowledged in the MR that the operators cannot be solely made responsible for achieving the OTs. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators to make progress in this MR. However, it is difficult to see any specific incentives and/or sanctions for Operators to archives the identified OTs.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

There are no OT related to socioeconomics and nor are there any information provided to enable an ex ante sensitivity analysis of the impact or consequence of the proposed OTs. This is an essential recommendation of the Audit Framework for RFMS in order to obtain increased likelihood of support to the MR from all relevant stakeholders.

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND RISKS

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address the main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized, and the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MR relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”¹⁸..

MR1 of SWA recommends a soft-law mechanism in the form of an International Conference on sustainable management in the SWA, which will contribute to a structured dialogue among stakeholders operating in the area. The conference is designed as a driver to facilitate further

¹⁸ Deliverable 4.4. p. 28

cooperation steps at international level and the agenda will include topics where common understanding could be easily developed, for instance in relation to scientific advances or priority topics such as the Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems. The conference may play as a dialogue initiative between stakeholders involved in fisheries of SWA. However, this may not be an effective mechanism to sustain the fisheries in SWA if the conference is organized as a single event. In addition, the challenges and incentive of getting operators involved is not addressed. The auditor recommends that the outcome of the conference should include a joint statement and guideline of sustainable fisheries practice in SWA.

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT RECCOMENDATION

The management goals, OTs and indicators developed in MR1 for South-West Atlantic are described in Table 4, as well as the defined indicators for these OTs.

Table 4: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets and indicators of CS SWA

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries	Initiate dialogue between stakeholders involved in fishery in FAO area 41 to support a level-playing field	OT 1.1 Develop a soft-law mechanism [e.g. Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41)	I_1_CS1: Number of invited stakeholders attending the Conference Indicator score: A I_2_CS1: Conference held Indicator score: C
Improved monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS)	Supporting enforcement by utilizing latest available satellite systems and tools	OT 1.2 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals	I_3_CS1: Operator compliance Indicator score: C
	Supporting the international cooperation on MCS	OT 1.3 Set a pilot project on operational coordination through the development of a Specific Control and Inspection Programme	I_4_CS1: Pilot Project launched Indicator score: C
Sustainable ecosystem	Protection of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems	OT 1.4 Both EU and non-EU fleet VMEs protection in accordance with UNGA 61/105 and FAO Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Waters in the High Seas	I_5_CS1: Operator compliance Indicator score: C

In order to make an initial dialogue between stakeholders, OT1.1 aims to develop a soft-law mechanism by organizing a conference focusing on sustainable management in SWA. Auditors consider this objective is necessary and achievable. However, MR should classify whether the conference is one time or a frequent conference (e.g. biennial or triennial conference). As European fleet (mainly Spanish vessels) harvest share only around 15% of the total value of landings (FarFish D3.4), the OT 1.1 should target to other operators including regional fleets (Argentina and Brazil) and other international fleets (Korea and China).

Indicator I_1_CS1 must be the number of participated operators instead of Invited stakeholders. Auditors suggest another indicator for this objective is the guideline book or conference proceeding focusing on sustainable fisheries in SWA, including the discussion among operators.

The EU fleet is committed to transmit both VMS and AIS signals. The tracking of AIS signals may also aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. As the EU fleet is already transmitting both VMS and AIS data, the reason for including this OT1.2 is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area to commit to VMS/AIS transmission as well, initiating a level playing field as has been requested by operators during the progress of developing this MR.

The OT1.3 is, as a first step, to conceptually develop a regional Specific control and inspection programme (SCIP) for international fleets operating in SWA with the view of being implemented in a second step through a Joint Deployment Plan (JDP) of control means either within the lifetime or after the life of the project. This OT is achieved by setting a pilot project on operational coordination through the development of a Specific Control and Inspection Programme.

The OT1.4 relates to the commitment to honour the VMEs for bottom trawlers based on scientific research and mapping in accordance with the Council Regulation (EC) No 734/2008 and thereby implementing a precautionary approach. This obligation is already being implemented by the EU fleet in line with (EC) Council Regulation No 734/2008. The reason for them being included as OTs is to make a comparative assessment of the reporting obligations among fleets and put increased pressure on responsibility of Flag States with fleets operating in the area to comply with these restrictions as well and thereby establish a level-playing field for EU and Non-EU fleet.

The Audit questions why C is used for indicator scoring for OT1.2, OT1.3 and OT1.4 instead of A/B, since C only contains a YES/NO measurability.

This leads to the SMART analysis of the OTs which is detailed in Table 5:

Table 5: SMART Analysis to OT1.2

Specific	Is fine for OT1.2
Measurable	What % of the fleet involved OT1.2?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions/costs will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what no of months/years shall the % be obtained?

With respect to OT1.3, setting a pilot project on operational coordination through the development of a Specific Control and Inspection Programme, the SMART analysis is presented below in Table 6:

Table 6: SMART Analysis to OT1.3

Specific	what is the reason of this pilot project and how to achieve the target?
Measurable	How to measure the success of the project?
Assignable	who is responsible to set up and coordinate the project?
Relevant	What cost will occur? And who will pay the cost?
Time	Within what is time period of the pilot project?

With respect to OT1.4, the questions regarding the formulation of this OT under the SMART analysis are presented in Table 7:

Table 7: SMART Analysis to OT1.4

Specific	It is not clear how to put increased pressure on responsibility to comply with the restrictions?
Measurable	What % of the fleet?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what no of months/years shall the % be obtained?

3.1.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been formulated and OT for socio-economic aspects in the MR1 for SWA no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 8 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 9.

Table 8: Documentation system conformance for South-West Atlantic

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.		CRITERIA 3. Pilot monitoring programs complement the information control measures.	
Outcome Target	Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria	
OT 1.1. Develop a soft-law mechanism [e.g. Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41) OT Dimension: Sustainable	There is no RFMO in place for the area with the legal competence to regulate demersal or deep-water fisheries, although the area falls under the convention area of ICCAT and CCBT.		The cost of developing a soft-law mechanism (e.g. international conference) is not detailed in the MR. The auditor assumes that the costs are paid by Authorities.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.	N/A
OT 1.2 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals OT Dimension: Governance	There are already several management measures related to OT 1.2 (Transmission of VMS signals).		The financial resources (or sanctions if no-compliance) are not detailed in the MR. The auditor assumes that costs are paid by Operators.		The test /check of commitment should be described in the MR in order to evaluate it properly.	
OT 1.3 Set a pilot project on operational coordination through the development of a Specific Control and Inspection Programme OT Dimension: Governance	The reason behind this OT is not described explicitly. Additionally, it is unclear if the OT set a theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO 41 as basis for a future pilot project or set a pilot project as a joint deployment plan for this region?		The financial resource for this pilot project is not detailed. The auditor assumes the costs are paid by Authority		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR	N/A
OT 1.4 Both EU and non-EU fleet VMEs protection in accordance with UNGA 61/105 and FAO Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Waters in the High Seas OT Dimension: Ecological	This obligation is already implemented by the EU fleet in line with (EC) Council Regulation No 734/2008. The reason to include these as OTs is for a comparative assessment of the reporting obligations among fleets and increase pressure on responsibility of Flag States with fleets in the area, to comply with these restrictions and establish level-playing field for EU and Non-EU fleet.		The financial resources (or sanctions if no-compliance) are not detailed in the MR. The auditor assumes that costs are paid by Authorities.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR	N/A

Table 9: Summary of the Evaluation of Management Recommendation for SWA

	Phase	Rating	MR1 _{SWA}	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3	
Step 1 MR Implementation	Documentation system	Risk level	OT1, OT4		N/A		
	Documentation system	Risk level	OT2				
	Documentation system	Risk level	OT3		N/A		
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline		Lack of data for PCBA			
		Alternative MR		Lack of data for PCBA			
		Optimistic scenario		Lack of data for PCBA			
		Pessimistic scenario		Lack of data for PCBA			

3.2 Case Study 2: South-East Atlantic

3.2.1 Documentation System Conformance

The Management Recommendations (MR1^{*}) invitation for this area was extended to the following European operators conducting mixed fishery in FAO area 47 in the South East Atlantic: LDAC, ADAPI, ANFACO-CECOPECA, OPAGAC and OPROMAR. The MR invitation states that there is very limited fishing activity conducted in the waters beyond areas of national jurisdiction within the FAO Area 47 (under the jurisdiction of SEAFO), and it is mostly conducted within two subareas B1 and D1, as specified in the MR invitation document (FarFish, 2019b). In recent years and in 2017, only two Spanish vessels showed some activity but no reported catches. Other fleets operating in the SEAFO CA in 2017 were Japan and Namibia. The only species targeted species in 2017 were *Patagonian toothfish* (Japan; 12 tonnes), *alfonsino* (Namibia, <1 tonnes), *deep sea crab* (Japan; 140 tonnes; Namibia, 7 tonnes) and *pelagic armourhead* (Namibia, <1). However, a MR was developed by the operator and approved by the authority, therefore the Auditor assumes that the following questions in Table 10, as defined in the checklist for the operators in the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019a), have been reviewed by the Authority. The table shows a summary of the Auditor's review for each item on the checklist i.e. whether each item is considered adequately addressed, partly addressed or not sufficiently addressed.

* 1st version MR

Table 10: Authority Checklist for MR1 for South-East Atlantic

1.	Have you proposed a management strategy and identified measures that make it clear how you intend to achieve the obligatory OTs mentioned in section 3 of the MR guideline?	Yes
2	Have you identified risks and uncertainties regarding the above-mentioned strategy, and have you explained how it may be adapted?	Yes
3	Have you explained how it will be ensured that individual participants will comply with the measures identified in the plan?	No
4	Do you have a strategy for monitoring fisheries activities?	No
5	In case that it is found that some participants do not comply with agreed measures, have you identified sanctions that reflect the severity of likely or foreseeable offences?	Partially
6	Have you described how information will be collected that allows for an audit of whether or not the OTs are achieved? It is clear who will collect each type of data, and is it clear when they should do this?	Yes
7	Have you agreed with the authority on who will serve as auditor, and how its service will be paid?	Yes
8	Is it clear how responsibility will be divided between “authority”, “operators” and “auditor”? Is it clear when each agency should carry out each of their tasks, and is it clear who should cover the costs of this?	Yes
9	Have you explained how the members of your organization(s) have been informed and involved in decision-making regarding the MR development?	Partially
10	Is it clear how adequate communication between the agencies (“assessors”, “authorities” and “operators”) is ensured?	Yes

According to the auditor, points 3 and 4 are not addressed and points 5 and 9 are partially covered in the MR1 for SEA. These points will be elaborated throughout the audit process.

Within the RFMS process, there are three main entities that have specific roles and responsibilities, namely the authorities, operators and auditors. MR1 for SEA describes the roles of these entities as required in the General Guidelines (FarFish, D3.1). The auditor will review the clarity and specificity in describing the authority and operators for SEA:

AUTHORITY

In FarFish, MATIS, acts as the leading authority, whilst considering input from the relevant authorities, e.g. South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation (SEAFO), coastal states and DG Mare. As there has been no fishing activity by European flagged vessels in the SEAFO area in recent years, this MR1 will be mostly theoretical.

OPERATOR

WP4 acting as operators, led by WP4 with major involvement from the task contributors, NOFIMA, IMR and UCAM. WP4 will also consider input from relevant operators e.g. LDAC. Since MR1 sets the European operators qualified to respond to the MR Invitation and will provide feedback through the Distance Advisory Council (LDAC).

Although the MR1 doe SEA is mostly theoretical in order to contribute or illustrate good practice in the fisheries, strive to involve all vessels fishing in this area is fundamental to promote level-playing fields.

If not, then each vessel/skipper can choose to be managed under RFMS or not. This fact could cause:

- Increase of management and monitoring cost for operator as well for Authority.
- Lack of trust in the system due to the absence of level playing field.
- The impact of the MR and its contributions to the overall management objectives would be reduced.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION

The aim of this MR is to serve good practice recommendations, focusing on improved monitoring for sustainable fisheries in the SEAFO convention area to support maintenance of international framework for future use and protection. The SEAFO is a modern and well-functioning RFMO, operating in an area with limited capacity of coastal states and managing fisheries on poor data stocks. SEAFO has in place a well-developed monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) system. The management of the SEAFO fisheries is therefore well suited to function as a showcase and illustrate good practice recommendations, committing both authorities and operators.

MR PLANNING PERIOD

The active participation of operators allows FarFish to have a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021). For the SEA and according to the planning period described, some actions have already taken place in order to achieve OT2.1 in terms of proposal with a strategy to undertake by August 2019 and for OT2.2 the data collection and diagnosis by September 2019. The auditor requests that the actions described in the planning period, their development and results are described thoroughly in MR2 to evaluate performance of the suggested actions.

INCENTIVES and SANCTIONS

MR1 clearly states that SEAFO has in place mechanisms that can be utilize for compliance and sanctions, however the auditor observes a lack of explicit connection between the existing sanctions in SEAFO and the achievement of OTs in FarFish project. In section 5.2, an attempt was made to describe how the FarFish action can be monitored, however it lacks to connect the actions to potential reports to SEAFO that can thereafter enforce actions through their sanction system, especially for OT2.2. The auditor considers that for the compliance and sanction mechanism to be applicable and useful for the RFMS, they need to be clearly related, in terms of which specific actions could be

undertaken for the relevant contracting parties fishing in the described area, if they do not comply with the actions described in the MR1. If mechanisms are in place and contribute to achieve the OTS of MR1, even if the FarFish project cannot enforce them, this should be stated in the document to strengthen it.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

The MR1 describes an area with considerably low fishing activity with only two vessels actively fishing in 2018. For the EU fleet, only two of five vessels from Spain showed some activity in the area yet did not reported any catches. This low level of activity poses important questions on the relevance and socioeconomic viability of the present MR1. However, MR1 does not present any OT related to socio-economics, neither provides any information to enable an ex ante sensitivity analysis of the impact or consequence of the proposed OTs. This is an essential recommendation of the Audit Framework for RFMS in order to obtain increased likelihood of support to the MR1 from all relevant stakeholders.

ECOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY

There is no OT related to ecological sustainability, despite this is a fundamental element of the RFMS, also considering that MR1 states that there is limited knowledge about the stock of the main targeted species in the area such as the *alfonsino* and the *pelagic armourhead* and one of them is consider overexploited, like the deep-sea crab, which implies than even with low fishing activity the stock can be overexploited and therefore, the fishing in the area could be better monitored.

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND RISKS

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address main risk and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized ant the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MP (MR) relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”¹⁹.

The risks and management strategies to achieving the obligatory OT2.1 and OT2.1, as well as the recommended OT2.3 are clearly stated in the document. However, for SEA CS there are important risks that should be addressed in order to achieve the OTs. Although the MR1 aims to be theoretical, there are important questions regarding the applicability and relevance of some the suggested actions, for instance the MR1 mentions that the current operators have limited control over the OTs, which questions the applicability of the MR1 for SEA CS, since according to the nature of the RFMS the operators should have some degree of control over the described OTs. The SMART analysis for the OTs and indicators that follows, will provide further remarks on the audit framework results.

¹⁹Deliverable 4.4. p. 28

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT RECCOMENDATION

The management goals, OTs and indicators developed in MR1 for South-East Atlantic are described in Table 11, as well as the defined indicators for these OTs.

Table 11: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets and their indicators for SEA

Management goal	Management objective	Outcome target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries based on the best scientific advice.	Improve the knowledge base for sustainable fisheries management.	OT2.1: Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks. OT Dimension: Governance.	I_1_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e logbooks.
			I_2_CS2: Initiate a dialogue meeting between SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country.
Sustainable fisheries by supporting the fight against IUU fisheries.	Improve monitoring and control.	OT2.2: Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals. OT Dimension: Governance.	I_3_CS2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated.
			I_4_CS2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation.

Table 12: Summary of Indicators, their category, baseline and the entity responsible for SEA

Outcome Target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator category	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 2.1	I_1_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e logbooks.	C	0	Authority, Task 4.3 contributors.
	I_2_CS2: Initiate a dialogue meeting between SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country.	C	0	
OT 2.2	I_3_CS2: Proportion of vessels, either EU of non-EU, geolocated.	B	4	Authority, SEAFO.
	I_4_CS2: Proportion of vessels, either EU of non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation.	A	0%	Authority, SEAFO.

OT2.1 states the obligation to “Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks” the current obligation is to all authorized vessels in the area to submit their logbook data, yet the challenge is that some countries have problems with VMS requirements according to SEAFO and although many fleets transmit AIS data there are still gaps according to recent reports Global Fishing Watch as stated in MR1. As the EU fleet is obliged to submit e-logbooks to their flag state under CFP and due to the problems with level playing-field, the OT2.1. should be assignable not only to the EU-fleet operating in the area but ensure that all countries comply.

Moreover, for OT2.1 the MR1 states that SEAFO does not have the system available to introduce an e-logbook system, which is also mentioned in the risks for achieving OT2.1, which will require investment, capacity building and new procedures. Altogether, with the low fishing activity in the area, this auditor considers that OT2.1 is unlikely to be achieved in practice since resources for this OT appear not to be available and can only serve a hypothetical situation of increased fishing activity. The auditor questions whether conducting this exercise is beneficial and serves the purposes of the RFMS and the FarFish project. The SMART analysis for OT2.1. is presented below in Table 13.

Table 13: SMART Analysis to OT2.1

Specific	Yes
Measurable	What % of the fleet is involved OT2.1?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible. Not clear if all countries are to comply
Relevant	Not clear of cost-beneficial for area due to high investment needed to apply e-logbook system and low fisheries. Specify how theoretical approach can benefit RFMS in the area and to what level of fisheries is needed to increase relevance.
Time	Within what Nr of months/years shall the OT be completed?

Considering the audit results of OT2.1, a further analysis should be conducted for the indicators that are set to measure this OT. Indicator I_1_CS2: “Develop a pilot project to introduce e logbooks.” in Table 14. Table 30

Table 14: SMART Analysis to I_1_CS4

Specific	what is the specific aim of this pilot project, what is the expected product and how to achieve the target?
Measurable	How to measure the success of the project?
Assignable	who is responsible to set up and coordinate the project? How can the outcome of the pilot project be effectively applied for all fleets?
Relevant	What cost will occur? And who will pay the cost?
Time	Within what is time period of the pilot project?

Indicator I_2_CS2 aims to “Initiate a dialogue meeting between SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country”, however this indicator lacks specificity and it is not clear what is the meaning of “contracting party defined as a developing country”. The auditor also questions if initiating the dialogue will suffice to indicate success of the OT2.1. The auditor questions therefore the category C for this indicator and considers that for this dialogue to be effective all relevant parties should participate, or a representative percentage of representation of the active operators, allowing category A for a redefined indicator in terms of participants to the dialogue. Measuring the number of participants or indicate if the dialogue will continue once it was installed, i.e. in terms of frequency of the dialogue, could give more accurate indication of the possibilities of success of this OT. The SMART analysis is presented below in Table 16:

Table 15: SMART Analysis to I_2_CS2

Specific	what is the specific aim of this dialogue and who or whom are the contracting party defined as a developing country
Measurable	How to measure the success of the dialogue?
Assignable	who is responsible to set up and coordinate the dialogue? How can success from the dialogue be established?
Relevant	What cost will occur? And who will pay the cost?
Time	Within what is time period will the dialogue take place? How often should it take place

With respect to OT2.2, The EU fleet is committed to transmit both VMS and AIS signals. The tracking of AIS signals may also aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. As the EU fleet is already transmitting both VMS and AIS data, the reason for including this OT1.2 is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area to commit to VMS/AIS transmission as well, initiating a level playing field as has been requested by operators during the progress of developing this MR. The SMART analysis is presented below in Table 16:

Table 16: SMART Analysis to OT2.2

Specific	Is adequate for OT 2.2
Measurable	What % of the fleet involved OT2.2?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions/costs will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what no of months/years shall the % be obtained?

3.2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been formulated and OT for socio-economic aspects in the MR1 for SEA no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 17 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 18.

Table 17: Documentation system conformance for South-East Atlantic

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators	CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.	CRITERIA 3. Pilot monitoring programs complement the information control measures
Outcome Target	Evidence-based for criteria	Evidence-based for criteria	Evidence-based for criteria
OT2.1: Reporting of all catches via E-logbooks. OT Dimension: Governance.	The described indicators don't seem to provide clear information on what extend can the OT be achieved. Indicators need to be more specific.	The financial costs and resources needed for implementing this mechanism seem to overcome the benefits from it due to low fishing activity	No monitoring programmes were included in the MR. N/A
OT 2.2 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals OT Dimension: Governance	There are already several management measures related to OT2.2 (Transmission of VMS signals).	The financial resources (or sanctions if no-compliance) are not detailed in the MR. The auditor assumes that costs are paid by Operators.	The test /check of commitment should be described in the MR in order to evaluate it properly.

Table 18: Summary of the Evaluation of Management Recommendation for SEA

	Phase	Rating	MR1_SEA	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3
Step 1	Documentation system	Risk level	OT1		N/A	
MR Implementation	Documentation system	Risk level	OT2			
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Alternative MR	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Optimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Pessimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			

3.3 Case Study 3: Cape Verde

3.3.1 Documentation System Conformance

The management recommendation (MR) is proposed for the tuna fishery under the SFPA agreement between Cape Verde and the European Union (EU). The MR1* follows the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019a) and is based on the Management Invitation (FarFish, 2019b) where the OTs are proposed.

As the MR has been delivered to the auditor, this means the document has been approved by the authority, therefore the Auditor assumes that the following questions in Table 19, as defined in the checklist for the operators in the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019a) have been reviewed by the Authority. The table shows a summary of the Auditor's review for each item on the checklist i.e. whether each item is considered adequately addressed, partly addressed or not sufficiently addressed.

Table 19: Auditor's review on MR proposal checklist for Cape Verde

1.	Have you proposed a management strategy and identified measures that make it clear how you intend to achieve the obligatory OTs mentioned in section 3 of the MR guideline?	Yes
2	Have you identified risks and uncertainties regarding the above-mentioned strategy, and have you explained how it may be adapted?	Yes
3	Have you explained how it will be ensured that individual participants will comply with the measures identified in the plan?	Yes
4	Do you have a strategy for monitoring fisheries activities?	No
5	In case that it is found that some participants do not comply with agreed measures, have you identified sanctions that reflect the severity of likely or foreseeable offences?	Partly
6	Have you described how information will be collected that allows for an audit of whether or not the OTs are achieved? It is clear who will collect each type of data, and is it clear when they should do this?	Yes
7	Have you agreed with the authority on who will serve as auditor, and how its service will be paid?	Yes
8	Is it clear how responsibility will be divided between "authority", "operators" and "auditor"? Is it clear when each agency should carry out each of their tasks, and is it clear who should cover the costs of this?	Partly
9	Have you explained how the members of your organization(s) have been informed and involved in decision-making regarding the MR development?	No
10	Is it clear how adequate communication between the agencies ("assessors", "authorities" and "operators") is ensured?	Yes

* 1st version MR

In the MR1 for Cape Verde points 5 and 8 are partially covered and points 4 and 9 are not covered in MR1. The review will be elaborated throughout the audit document.

The MR1 for Cape Verde should describe the roles of the entities within the RFMS as required in the General Guidelines (FarFish, 2019a). The auditor will review the clarity and specificity in describing the authority and operators for this CS:

AUTHORITIES

MATIS, that acts as the leading authority, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. the National Directorate of Maritime Economy (DNEM), General Directorate for Marine Resources (DGRM) and Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). The main contact person in this process is Jónas R. Viðarsson²⁰ from WP3, as the leader of Task 3.3.

OPERATOR

The European operator qualified to respond to the MR Invitation for Cape Verde are the Long-Distance Advisory Council²¹ (LDAC) and Organization de Palangreros Guardeses (ORPAGU) which represents surface long liners from Spain²². LDAC is an EU fisheries stakeholder led body represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodriguez²³. LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of the fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs).

The auditor encountered other relevant operators described in Table 2.1 in the MR1 for Cape Verde, namely ANFACO-CECOPECA and OPAGAC. However, it is not clear in the text of the MR1 whether these organizations are involved since only LDCA and ORPAGU are mentioned. The auditor suggests to the organizations involved are clearly stated and that the information is coherent both in text and in tables provided.

MR1 provides clear numbers in terms of the EU fleet accessing fishing opportunities in Cape Verde EEZ by gear and country detailed in Table 3.1 in this document. The EU fleet is from Spain, Portugal and France and consist of pole and line vessels, tuna seiners and surface long liners. Also, numbers of non-EU vessels are provided in text, by gear and country.

However, due to the voluntary nature of participating in the RFMS, it is not clear which vessels will be finally involved. A list with the implicated vessels is recommended to be presented at the beginning of the MR, which could be updated at the end of the year, if necessary.

Also, from the MR description It is not clear to what extent all vessels of the same fishing organisation will accept and participate in the MR. Is the assumption that if a fishing association agrees to join in a RFMS'

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MR, all their members (vessels or skippers) accept the MR? If not, then each vessel/skipper can choose to be managed under RFMS or not. This fact could cause:

- Increase of management and monitoring cost for operator as well for Authority.
- Lack of trust in the system due to the absence of same level playing field.
- The impact of the MR and its contributions to the overall management objectives would be reduced.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION 1 FOR CAPE VERDE

The main goal of MR1 for Cape Verde is to improve data collection and monitoring for sustainable fisheries, especially for the species of blue shark and swordfish, as there is high uncertainty in the data provided and the catch data from EU, Cape Verde and ICCAT diverge some years. The background for this main goal is the need to harmonize catch data protocols to ensure that the best scientific data is collected and made available for authorities and the relevant scientific institutions, including ICCAT. This also applies for bycatches, as blue shark is still considered such in the current SFPAs agreement (2014-2018). The insufficient control and monitoring in relation to foreign vessels in Cape Verde EEZ, are obstacles to the fight against IUU fisheries.

The main challenges identified in the Cape Verde Fisheries Management Plan (PGRP) for the foreign fleet are: 1) non-compliance by foreign vessels, 2) insufficient control and monitoring, and 3) competition with the national commercial fleet(s). The specific challenges to be addressed in the MR1 for Cape Verde are the high level of uncertainty in data collection and the insufficient control and monitoring in the Cape Verde EEZ.

According to this auditor, the challenges identified in the Cape Verde highly depend on active participation and commitment from all relevant operators. However, according to the description of participating operator, it is established that there are no representatives from foreign vessels/operators included in the MR. The list of non-EU vessels operating the Cape Verde waters, apart from the domestic fleet, are from Japan (8 longliners), Senegal (4 purse seiners, 2 pole & liners), El Salvador (4 purse seiners), Curacao (3 purse seiners), Panama (2 purse seiners) and Belize (1 purse seine vessel). MR1 mentions that all these countries are ICCAT contracting parties (CP), which oblige them to provide available statistical, biological and other scientific information and comply with recommendations and resolutions. However, there is no clear means of interaction with these vessels in order to follow up the application of the OTs from this MR1, which raises an important question about how the main challenges identified can be properly addressed with the MR1. The auditor highlights the need to suggest protocols of interaction with international and local fleet representatives. A clear protocol for adhering and leaving the RFMS and a conflict resolution mechanism can contribute to promoting participation in this MR1.

MR PLANNING PROCESS

The active participation of operators allows FarFish to have a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021). It is worth mentioning, that MR1 states that, it is not up to the operators to address the issues raised in MR1. The authorities (WP3) are mostly responsible for the progress towards achieving the OTs and the roles for FarFish partners WP2 and WP6 are clearly defined in Table 8.1 in MR1 document. Also, this section states clearly the deadlines and expected outcomes for both OTs. The auditor suggests that since these detailed information and time plans are provided in the document, this level of clarity could be included in the correspondent OTs to fulfil the SMART formulation requirements. This suggestion will be specified in the audit of the individual OTs and indicators below.

The auditor emphasizes the importance of striving for the participation of all EU vessels actively participating in this fishery to ensure OTs can be fully applicable and achieved. Efforts on finding communication channels with foreign fleet is also relevant. The auditor encounters a lack of description on how the operators will agree to enter the data harmonization initiative and how to resolve potential conflicts, in case they emerge, as mentioned above, a concise plan including all previously mentioned factors could promote participation from the whole fleet in the RFMS and strengthen this MR1. It is acknowledged that participation is voluntary, however good practices are recommended to ensure due diligence, transparency and good governance in the RFMS process.

MONITORING, COMPLIANCE AND SANCTIONS

In general, the MR1 lack descriptions of incentives and sanctions in relation to the OTs. It is acknowledged in the MR1 that the operators are not solely responsible for achieving the OTs and that the authority is mostly in charge. However, the operators are responsible for OT1 provide the necessary documentation for harmonization process and for OT4 transmitting the data required. The auditor finds a lack of monitoring and control clearly stated in this MR1. However, the management measures define clear and strict monitoring mechanisms for data transmission recommended by ICCAT, for example those stated in MR1 document in section 5.2.1.1 in regards of the blue shark fishery and in section 5.2.1.3 in regards of data transmission. This section mentioned specific sanction and control mechanisms for not fulfilling the data exchange. The document could clearly state how these mechanisms can be useful to strengthen monitoring of the OTs. The auditor also considers that MR lacks any specific incentives for Operators to collaborate in archiving the identified OTs.

ECOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY

There is no OT related to ecological sustainability, despite this is a fundamental element of the RFMS, and furthermore the MR1 for Cape Verde mentions aspects which could represent relevant ecological OT, e.g. the current MRs from ICCAT for SWO-N provides probability of maintaining $B < B_{msy}$ and maintaining $F < F_{msy}$ over a range of TAC options for a period of 10 years, where the current TAC of 13,200 tons would have a 50% probability of resulting in a biomass above the B_{msy} with a probability greater than 50% in Appendix 1, ICCAT, 2018 SCRS report (ICCAT, 2018).

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

There are no OT related to socio-economics and nor are there any information provided to enable an ex ante sensitivity analysis of the impact or consequence of the proposed OTs. This is an essential recommendation of the Audit Framework for RFMS in order to obtain increased likelihood of support to the MR from all relevant stakeholders.

STRATEGIES; MANAGEMENT AND RISKS

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address the main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized, and the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MR relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”²⁴. The auditor considers that the risks to achieving the obligatory OTs described in MR1 are adequately described. However, the risks that required following up and mitigation should clearly establish dates to control and follow up the evolution of the factors causing uncertainty i.e. for OT3.1 the late submission of format for harmonization and for OT3.4 the deterioration of quality of AIS data due to GFW awareness. On the other hand, the auditor finds that the MR establishes mechanisms to be adaptive and facilitate the implementation of the RFMS through this MR.

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION

The obligatory OTs are described in Table 20 as well as the defined indicators. For the indicators listed for Cape Verde, the auditor suggests unifying the code assigned to these across CS, the indicators code includes the CS number in the format *I_Nr_CSNr*.

²⁴ Deliverable 4.4. p. 28

Table 20: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets and indicators of CS Cape Verde

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries based on the best scientific advice (CFP (SFPA) PGRM, SDG 14, ICCAT)	Improved data collection, in conformity with ICCAT, collect and analyse data on bycatch of swordfish and blue shark	OT 3.1 A harmonised catch data protocol that facilitate improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data, in place Dimension: Ecological	I_1 Harmonised protocols in place
Sustainable fisheries by supporting the Fight against IUU fisheries (CFP (SFPA) PGRM, SDG 14, ICCAT)	Improved monitoring and control by supporting enforcement through utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools	OT 3.4 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals Dimension: Governance	I_2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated
			I_3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation

OT3.1 was rephrased at WP/CS leader meeting at Cape Verde, November 2018; aiming to make it more specific and in accordance with feedback from ICCAT who is responsible for the assessment of tuna and tuna like species in this case study.

The EU fleet is committed to transmit both VMS and AIS signals. The tracking of AIS signals may also aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. As the EU fleet is already transmitting both VMS and AIS data, the reason for including this OT 3.4 is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area²⁵ to commit to VMS/AIS transmission as well, initiating a level playing field as has been requested by operators during the progress of developing this MR.

²⁵ „The parties hereby undertake to promote responsible fishing in Cape Verdean waters on the basis of the principle of non-discrimination between the various fleets fishing in those waters. All technical conservation measures which must be met in order for a fishing licence to be issued, as specified in Appendix 2 of the Annex, shall apply to all

Table 21: Indicators related to obligatory OTs in MR1 for CS Cape Verde

Outcome Target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 3.1 A harmonised catch data protocol that facilitate improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data, in place	I_1 Harmonised protocols in place	C	0	Authority, WP2, CCMAR
OT 3.4 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals	I_2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated	A	0	Authority, WP6, CSIC
	I_3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation	A	0	Authority, WP6, CSIC

The indicators related to the obligatory OTs developed for Cape Verde are described in Table 21. The auditor questions why OT3.1 only has one indicator in category C. The OT1 has been described as having enough information for better following up the progress of this task. The auditor suggests exploring other indicators such as the number of formats analysed or harmonized in a given period of time from the total number of protocols in place. These indicators allow to provide specific numbers for scoring in category A, strengthening the following up and scoring of this OT.

For OT3.1 the operator ORPAGU suggests harmonizing SFPa and ICCAT data only relying on Flag and coastal states to submit data according to the EU and ICCAT in isolation. The auditor questions how this comment have been tackled to narrow down the harmonization task and focus on the relevant data information systems that are most relevant to harmonize.

Finally, specific management measures are relevant to OT3.1 from SFPa and in the Cape Verdean management plan as mentioned in section 5.2.1. These measures establish specific actions to control and monitor data exchange and collection, yet the OT3.1 does not mention or use any of these mechanisms in the formulation of this OT. This leads to the question of if the OT3.1. is formulated SMART, described further in Table 22:

Table 22: Smart analysis OT3.1

Specific	Is OK, since harmonised catch data protocol
Measurable	What % of the fleet?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what no of months/years shall the % be obtained?

For OT3.4, the auditor finds that the success of this OT depends on Cape Verde capability to process data, as it mentioned in MR1 the coastal state has problem with compatibility of the systems to process the transmitted data. The OT should specify how to follow up this compatibility issue with the national authority.

In addition, for OT3.4 specific management measures are relevant to OT3.4 from SFPa, the Cape Verdean management plan and within ICCAT as mentioned in section 5.2.2. These measures establish specific actions to control data transmission and sanctions for failure in doing so, yet the OT3.4 does not mention or use any of these mechanisms in the formulation of this OT. This leads to the question of if the OT3.4. is formulated SMART as shown in Table 23:

Table 23: SMART Analysis OT 3.4

Specific	Is OK, since transmission of VMS signals is clearly defined
Measurable	What % of the fleet?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what no of months/years shall the % be obtained?

3.3.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been formulated and OT for socio-economic aspects in the MR1 for Cape Verde no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 24 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 25.

Table 24: Documentation system conformance for Cape Verde

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.		CRITERIA 3. Pilot monitoring programs complement the information control measures.	
Outcome Target	Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria	
<p>OT 3.1 A harmonised catch data protocol that facilitate improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data, in place</p> <p>OT Dimension: Ecological</p>	Adapt management measures related to the current SFPA to PGRM and ICCAT. All EU vessels fishing under SFPA agreement must keep a fishing logbook (Appendix 4 in SFPA protocol) and all vessels fishing tuna must report nominal catch (Task I) and catch & effort data (Task II) sheets to ICCAT.		The allocation of resources for the adaption of management measures is not detailed in the MR. Personnel and financial resources involve EU Authorities, Cape Verde and Non-EU fishing fleet. Next surveillances should demonstrate (or not) if they are enough to provide the needed data.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.	n.a.
<p>OT 3.4 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals</p> <p>OT Dimension: Governance</p>	There are already a number of management measures related to OT 3.4 (Transmission of VMS signals) within the current SFPA, PGRM and ICCAT.		The financial resources (or sanctions if no-compliance) are not detailed in the MR. The auditor assumes that costs are paid by Operators.		The test /check of commitment should be described in the MR in order to evaluate it properly.	

Table 25: Summary of the Evaluation of Management Recommendation for Cape Verde

	Phase	Rating	MR1_ Cape Verde	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3
Step 1 MR Implementation	Documentation system	Risk level	OT3.1		NA	
			OT3.2			
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Alternative MR	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Optimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Pessimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			

3.4 Case Study 4: Senegal

3.4.1 Documentation System Conformance

This management recommendation (MR) is proposed for the black hake fishery under the SFPA agreement between Senegal and the EU. The EU vessels currently targeting black hake in Senegalese EEZ are trawlers from Spain. The MR1* for Senegal indicates that two different species of black hake are targeted and that there is a lack of distinction between the two in catch reports, observers' reports and catch statistics. The two black hake species are assessed as one by the Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries (CECAF).

Accordingly, the main stages in the MR development process in RFMS include the authority's invitation for a MR, the operator's development of a MR proposal, and the authority's 'quality check' of this proposal and the RFMS planning process overall. As the MR for Senegal has been approved, the auditor assumes that the following questions in Table 26 have been reviewed by the Authority. The table shows a summary of the Auditor's review for each item on the checklist i.e. whether each item is considered adequately addressed, partly addressed or not sufficiently addressed.

Table 26: Auditor's review on MR1 proposal checklist for Senegal CS

1.	Have you proposed a management strategy and identified measures that make it clear how you intend to achieve the obligatory OTs mentioned in section 3 of the MR guideline?	Yes
2	Have you identified risks and uncertainties regarding the above-mentioned strategy, and have you explained how it may be adapted?	Partially
3	Have you explained how it will be ensured that individual participants will comply with the measures identified in the plan?	Yes
4	Do you have a strategy for monitoring fisheries activities?	No
5	In case that it is found that some participants do not comply with agreed measures, have you identified sanctions that reflect the severity of likely or foreseeable offences?	No
6	Have you described how information will be collected that allows for an audit of whether or not the OTs are achieved? It is clear who will collect each type of data, and is it clear when they should do this?	Partially
7	Have you agreed with the authority on who will serve as auditor, and how its service will be paid?	Yes
8	Is it clear how responsibility will be divided between "authority", "operators" and "auditor"? Is it clear when each agency should carry out each of their tasks, and is it clear who should cover the costs of this?	Yes
9	Have you explained how the members of your organization(s) have been informed and involved in decision-making regarding the MR development?	Partially
10	Is it clear how adequate communication between the agencies ("assessors", "authorities" and "operators") is ensured?	Yes

* 1st version MR

The auditors consider that points 4 and 5 are not addressed or and points 2, 6 and 9 are partially covered in the MR1 for Senegal.

AUTHORITIES

MATIS, as the leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS) in FarFish, acts as the leading authority of the Senegal case study, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs (MPAM) and DG MARE. The auditor evaluates that a research institute plays as a representative authority will help the MR proceed quick and more on research based. However, the risk of the representative authority is that the MR may not reflect the reality and expectation of the acted authority. Therefore, the communication between MATIS, MPAM and DG MARE must be taken played. The discussion from the meetings must be documented and provided in MR appendix.

OPERATOR

The European operators qualified to respond to the first MR Invitation for Senegal on OTs related to black hake are the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR). LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of the fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is represented by other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs). OPROMAR represents 35 fishing companies including demersal trawlers, surface longliners and purse-seiners vessels. Currently, there are only two European trawlers operating in the Senegalese EEZ under the license based on the terms of the SFPA, targeting black hake.

The leader of work package 4 (WP4) in FarFish, UiT - The Arctic University of Norway, assists the representatives for operators in the development of the MR1.

Due to the voluntary role of participating in the RFMS, it is not clear which vessels will be finally involved. A list with the implicated vessels is recommended to be presented at the beginning of the MR, which could be updated at the end of the year, if necessary.

From the MR description it is not clear to what extent all vessels of the same fishing organisation will accept and participate in the MR. Is the assumption that if a fishing association agrees to join in a RFMS' MR, all their members (vessels or skippers) accept the MR?

If not, then each vessel/skipper can choose to be managed under RFMS or not. This fact could cause:

- Increase of management and monitoring cost for operator as well for Authority.
- Lack of trust in the system due to the absence of same level playing field.
- The impact of the MR and its contributions to the overall management objectives would be reduced.

MAIN GOAL WITH THE MR

The aims of the MR1 for Senegal is to improve data collection and monitoring, especially for bycatch and for the proportion of the two black hake species in catch; and to improve monitoring and control by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools. This MR1 applies to the EU Fishery for deep-sea demersal fishery targeting mainly black hake in Senegal EEZ, FAO subdivision 34.3.11, 34.3.12 and 34.3.13. The black hake fishery target two different species, Tropical African hake (*Merluccius polli*) and Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*). There is a lack of knowledge about the proportion of the two species caught in Senegalese waters. To support sustainable fisheries, FarFish aim is to address the availability of bycatch data in the black hake fishery, enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches and support the fight against illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU) in Senegalese EEZ.

This MR1 applies to only EU fishery, which is represented by the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR), targeting two black hake species. The auditor questions why MR1 sets these aims limits to only European fisheries? Currently there are only two EU trawlers authorized to fish in the Senegalese EEZ, operating under the license based on the terms of the SFPA, targeting black hake (FarFish MR1-Senegal). Therefore, there is a risk regarding the compliance and effectiveness of the MR. Assuming that all European fishers accept and obey the agreement of MR, the main goal i.e. improving data collection, monitoring to support the fight against IUU may not be achieved if other fisheries would not cooperate.

In addition, EU fisheries in Senegal have been monitored by the Joint Scientific Committee (CSC) on the Fisheries Agreement between Senegal and EU. The committee has made several recommendations for EU fishery under Category 1: Deep demersal species (mostly black hake). CSC also recommend a more frequent monitoring of the productivity of black hake at a regional level by reinforcement of the data collection via fishing journals and the placement of observer programmes onboard hake fishing vessels, thus in all the vessels where black hake occurs, specifically by the vessels targeting shrimp (both high seas and coastal), regardless of flag state (Farfish-MR1). However, there are difficulties in regarding to the implementing obligations/agreement.

MR PLANNING PERIOD

The active participation of operators allows FarFish to have a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021).

INCENTIVES and SANCTIONS

In general, the MR1 of Senegal lack descriptions of incentives and sanctions in relation to the OTs, and the measures coping with the incompliance of non-EU fisheries. It is acknowledged in the MR that the operators cannot be solely made responsible for achieving the OTs. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators to make progress in this MR. However, it is difficult to see any specific incentives and/or sanctions for Operators to archives the identified OTs. As mentioned above, there are currently a Joint Scientific Committee (CSC) on the Fisheries Agreement between Senegal

and EU that has made several recommendations regarding data collection, monitoring and inspection. However, there are difficulties in implementing these recommendations and regulations. It may be due to lack of incentives and sanctions.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

There are no OT related to socio-economics and nor are there any information provided to enable an ex ante sensitivity analysis of the impact or consequence of the proposed OTs. This is an essential recommendation of the Audit Framework for RFMS in order to obtain increased likelihood of support to the MR from all relevant stakeholders.

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND RISKS

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address the main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized, and the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MR relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”.

In general, the risks and strategies to achieving OTs in MR1 are well addressed. However, these strategies and risks are mentioned and suggested for both EU and Non-EU vessels while main goals of MR are only for EU fisheries targeting black hake species.

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION

Table 27 describes the obligatory OTs developed in MR1 for the black hake fisheries in Senegal, as well as the defined indicators.

Table 27: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets and indicators of CS Senegal

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries (SFPA), Conserve and Sustainable use of the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development (SDG 14)	Improved quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 4.1 Make bycatch data available OT Dimension: Ecological	I_1_CS4: Bycatch data specified by operators in fishing logbook to IEO and/or CRODT. Indicator score: C
			I_2_CS4: Observers report, including bycatch data made available to IEO and/or CRODT and master of vessel. Indicator score: C
	Improved input data for sustainable and potentially separate stock assessment of the two species of black hake <i>M.palli</i> and <i>M.senegalensis</i>	OT 4.2 Provide information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches OT Dimension: Ecological	I_3_CS4: Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake Indicator score: A
			I_4_CS4: Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis. Indicator score: A
Improved monitoring and control	Support enforcement by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools	OT 4.3 Commitment to transmit VMS and/or AIS signals OT Dimension: Governance	I_6_CS4: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated Indicator score: B
			I_7_CS4: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation Indicator score: A

OT4.1 aims to make bycatch data available, by improving data collection and reporting from all operators in Senegalese waters where data on catches and landings of all species is reported via electronic reporting. This target is measured by two indicators: I_1_CS4: Bycatch data available by operators in fishing logbook to IEO and/or CRODT; and I_2_CS4: Report on bycatch data by scientific observers made available to IEO and/or CRODT. The auditor questions why these indicators will be measured as C category (Yes/No) instead of A category. The A category can be used to measure the probability or proportion of bycatch data that are specified and reported by operators and observers. These indicators should be formulated SMART analysed in Table 28.

Table 28: SMART Analysis to I_1_CS4 and I_2_CS4

Specific	Is fine for OT 4.1, since harmonised catch data protocol.
Measurable	What % of the operators and probability the observers are involved OT 4.1?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions/costs will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what number of months/years shall the information be obtained?

For OT4.2. three indicators are suggested to measure the performance: 1) I_3_CS4: Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake; 2) I_4_CS4: Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis; 3) I_5_CS4: Preliminary molecular analysis study to verify visual identification of black hake. These indicators are classified as A category in Table 27 but are not explained in text the reasons of that classification. In addition, auditor question that why “I_3_CS4: Training of Senegalese observers...” is classified into A category instead of B category, which indicates the level of training frequency.

In general, three indicators suggested to measure OT4.2 should be formulated SMART. The analysis for Indicator I_3_CS4 “Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake” is described in Table 29.

Table 29: SMART Analysis to I_3_CS4

Specific	is clear the intention of the indicator I_3_CS4, i.e. aiming to measure the probability of the training will happen or the number of training?
Measurable	What is the level of frequency of the training?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	is fine due to the lack of knowledge and experiences of Senegalese in species identification.
Time	when the training should be happened? It should be in the period of FarFish project.

Indicator I_4_CS4: “Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis” in Table 30

Table 30: SMART Analysis to I_4_CS4

Specific	Is clear
Measurable	How many samples?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What cost will occur? And who will pay the cost.
Time	when the sample taken?

With respect to I_5_CS4: “Preliminary molecular analysis study to verify visual identification of black hake” the analysis is described in Table 31.

Table 31: SMART Analysis to I_5_CS4

Specific	is not clear, especially the difference between indicators I_4 and I_5
Measurable	How many analyses or how often?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What cost will occur? And who will pay the cost
Time	when the analysis taken?

The **OT4.3** Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals, measured by two indicators: I_6_CS4 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geo-localization, and I_7_CS4 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS), geo-localization. The audit questions why I_6_CS4 is measured by B category and I_7_CS4 is measured by A category, while they are the same type of indicators. In addition, the indicators should be formulated more SMART as analysed in Table 32.

Table 32: SMART Analysis to I_6_CS4 and I_7_CS4

Measurable	proportion or probability?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What cost will occur? And who will pay the cost?
Time	Within what is time period of the pilot project?

3.4.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been formulated and OT for socio-economic aspects in the MR1 for Senegal no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 33 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 34.

Table 33: Documentation system conformance for Senegal

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.		CRITERIA 3. Pilot monitoring programs complement the information control measures	
Outcome Target	Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria	
OT 4.1 Make bycatch data available OT Dimension: Ecological	The observer reports are not made available and/or do not contain bycatch data.		The cost of making bycatch data available is not detailed in the MR. The auditor assumes that the costs are paid by Authorities.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.	N/A
OT 4.2 Provide information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches OT Dimension: Ecological	Due to their morphological resemblance and overlapping occurrence at certain depths, both species are mixed in catches and catch statistics. An improvement of the estimation of the proportion of <i>Merluccius polli</i> (HKB) and <i>Merluccius senegalensis</i> (HKM), will add value to a separated stock assessment		Preliminary estimated cost for molecular analysis for species identification is included, but the cost of training activity is not detail in MR.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR	N/A
OT 4.3 Commitment to transmit VMS and/or AIS signals OT Dimension: Governance	Although VMS has been mandatory since 2006 and Senegalese vessels and inspectors carry out monitoring and control at sea, the action plan requires external support to strengthening the means of fisheries surveillance and better coordination of interventions and actions at national level		The financial resource for this transmission VMS and AIS signals is not detailed in MR. The auditor assumes the costs are paid by Authority		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR	N/A
OT 4.4. Increase knowledge and data collection of all fleets operating in the Senegalese EEZ on trade flows. Recommended OT.	Currently, hake consumption in Senegal is limited, few markets exist for the species and the prices are low. Through increased effort in marketing activities, value-chain development and analysis, black hake could become an important contribution to local markets and social aspects.		The financial resource for this OT is not detail in MR. The auditor assumes the costs are paid by Authority		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR	N/A

Table 34: Summary of the Evaluation of Management Recommendation for Senegal

	Phase	Rating	MR1_ Senegal	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3
Step 1 MR Implementation	Documentation system	Risk level	OT1, OT2, OT3, OT4		N/A	
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Alternative MR	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Optimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Pessimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			

3.5 Case Study 5: Mauritania

3.5.1 Documentation System Conformance

This management recommendation (MR) applies to the EU fishery under the SFPAs agreement in Mauritania EEZ, FAO subdivision 34.3.11 and 31.1.32. The current SFPAs agreement between the Islamic Republic of Mauritania and EU covers the period from 2015 to 2019 and allows for several fleets and target shrimp, demersal fish, tuna and small pelagic fish. This MR1* for Mauritania focuses on the black hake fishery under the SFPAs agreement. The EU vessels currently targeting black hake are trawlers from Spain. Two different species of black hake are targeted under category 2 and 2bis under the SFPAs agreement (2015-2019), i.e. the tropical African black hake (*Merluccius polli*) and the Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*), but there is a lack of distinction between the two in catch statistics.

As the MR has been approved, the Auditor assumes that the questions listed in Table 35 have been reviewed by the Authority, according to the general guidelines (FarFish D3.1). The table shows a summary of the Auditor's review for each item on the checklist i.e. whether each item is considered adequately addressed, partly addressed or not sufficiently addressed.

Table 35: Auditor's review on MR1 Operator's checklist for Mauritania

1.	Have you proposed a management strategy and identified measures that make it clear how you intend to achieve the obligatory OTs mentioned in section 3 of the MR guideline?	Partially
2	Have you identified risks and uncertainties regarding the above-mentioned strategy, and have you explained how it may be adapted?	Partially
3	Have you explained how it will be ensured that individual participants will comply with the measures identified in the plan?	Partially
4	Do you have a strategy for monitoring fisheries activities?	No
5	In case that it is found that some participants do not comply with agreed measures, have you identified sanctions that reflect the severity of likely or foreseeable offences?	No
6	Have you described how information will be collected that allows for an audit of whether or not the OTs are achieved? It is clear who will collect each type of data, and is it clear when they should do this?	Yes
7	Have you agreed with the authority on who will serve as auditor, and how its service will be paid?	Yes
8	Is it clear how responsibility will be divided between "authority", "operators" and "auditor"? Is it clear when each agency should carry out each of their tasks, and is it clear who should cover the costs of this?	Yes
9	Have you explained how the members of your organization(s) have been informed and involved in decision-making regarding the MR development?	Partially
10	Is it clear how adequate communication between the agencies ("assessors", "authorities" and "operators") is ensured?	Partially

* 1st version MR

In the MR1 for Mauritania, the auditor considers that points 1, 2, 3, 9 and 10 are partially covered in MR1 since obligatory OTs for small pelagic and shrimp are not yet covered. Points 4 and 5 are not covered in MR1.

AUTHORITIES

MATIS, as the leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS) in FarFish, acts as the leading authority of the Mauritanian case study, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy (MPEM), the Management of Oceanic Resources (DARE) and the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). The auditor evaluates that a research institute plays as a representative authority will help the MR proceed quick and more on research based. However, the risk of the representative authority is that the MR may not reflect the reality and expectation of the acted authority. Therefore, the communication between MATIS, MPEM, DARE and DG MARE must be taken played. The discussion from the meetings must be documented and provided in MR appendix.

OPERATOR

The European operators qualified to respond to the first MR Invitation for Mauritania on OTs related to black hake are the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR). LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of the fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs). OPROMAR represents 35 fishing companies including demersal trawlers, surface longliners and purse-seiners vessels. Between 2-5 Spanish vessels have been fishing under *Category 2* in the last decade (FarFish, 2019h) and six Spanish vessels in under the new *Category 2bis* in 2018. Four trawlers from OPROMAR were actively operating under *Category 2* (fresh) and six trawlers under *Category 2bis* (frozen) in 2018. The leader of work package 4 (WP4) in FarFish, UiT - The Arctic University of Norway, assists the representatives for operators in the development of the MR1.

Considering the importance of participation in the RFMS and its voluntary nature, it should be clear which vessels from each of the categories will be involved and their allocated quota. The auditor recommends presenting a list with all the vessels that the MR should aim to include at the beginning of the MR, specifying size, gear type, target species and allocated quota, and whether or not they will be part of the MR. This list could be updated at the end of the year, if necessary.

In MR1 of Mauritania is not clearly mentioned to what extent all vessels of the same fishing organisation operating in this fishery will accept and participate in the MR. Is the assumption that if a fishing association agrees to join in a RFMS' MR, all their members (vessels or skippers) accept the MR? If not, then each vessel/skipper can choose to be managed under RFMS or not. This fact could cause:

- Increase of management and monitoring cost for operator as well for Authority.
- Lack of trust in the system due to the absence of same level playing field.
- The impact of the MR and its contributions to the overall management objectives would be reduced.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION 1 FOR MAURITANIA

This MR1 applies to the EU fishery of black hake caught under the SFPA agreement in Mauritania EEZ, FAO subdivision 34.3.11 and 31.1.32. Two different species of black hake are targeted under *category 2* and *2bis* under the SPFA agreement (2015-2019), i.e. the tropical African black hake (*Merluccius polli*) and the Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*), but considerable amounts of black hake is also taken as bycatch under other fleet categories, specially demersal other than black hake in *category 3* and pelagic trawler in *category 6* and *7*. The MR1 for Mauritania aims to improve knowledge on the species composition black hake in catches and thereby adding value to stock assessment for both species. To support sustainable fisheries, this MR1 aims to enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches. The black hake fisheries where given priority in the first loop by consensus between Authority and Operators. The development of MRs and OTs related to other fisheries such as small pelagic and the shrimp is said to require a differentiated strategy and will be further reinforced into the second loop.

Operators adhering to this MR1 include only EU fisheries, represented by the Long-Distance Advisory Council (LDAC) and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR), targeting the two black hake species. The auditor recognizes the relevance of the involved operators however, there is concern regarding relevant participation from other fleets targeting this species, including local fleet. The auditor also finds that from FarFish partner OPROMAR only fresh-fish trawlers from Category 2 have agreed to participate, as for 2018 there were four trawlers. Freezer trawlers fishing under category 2bis have not adhere, there were accounted six vessels operating in 2018. Lack of participation increases the risk regarding the compliance and effectiveness of the MR. Considering that at this point the European fleet has only partially accept and adhere to the MR, the main goals i.e. to improve knowledge and enhance data collection may not be achieved, if the complete European fleet and others, local and international would not adhere.

Moreover, black hake is a shared stock in the CECAF subregion Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and the Gambia which requires a regional approach, increasing the need to coordinate regional actions. The auditor finds similarities in the respective MR1 from Senegal and Mauritania and suggests mentioning the possibility of coordinated action in the two countries and extend the invitation to other countries involved in the black hake fishery, namely Morocco and the Gambia.

In addition, EU fisheries in Mauritania have been monitored by the Joint Scientific Committee (CSC) on the Fisheries Agreement between Mauritania and the EU and have several recommendations for the EU fishery under Category 2 and 2bis targeting black hake in Mauritania. The CSC recommends considering the stock status in the sub-region and refrain from increased fishing effort and catches,

aim for harmonizing data sources to properly estimate black hake mortality and recommends the organisation of a special workshop for the revision of the black hake data matrix. The Committee also recommended the reduction of accessory catches from other fisheries and clarify this bycatch data with the aim of estimating impacts on black hake stocks. Also, to implement a harmonized sampling protocol to differentiate the two species of black hake and a separate assessment of the two species.

MR PLANNING PROCESS

Active participation of representative members within the operators' organizations is critical to achieve a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021). In MR1 there is partial participation of the fleet represented by partner OPROMAR, with three fresh fish trawlers ensuring participation. The auditor emphasizes the importance of striving for the participation of the six freezer trawlers from this partner as well as from the Pelagic Freezer-trawler Association (PFA). Efforts on involving local fleet in all relevant categories, targeting and with accessory catches of black hake should be properly documented and reported. Also, the auditor encounters a lack of description on how the operators will agree to enter the data collection initiative and how to leave it, as well as how to resolve potential conflicts, in case they emerge, a concise plan to promote participation in the RFMS that includes all previously mentioned factors could strengthen this MR1. It is acknowledged that participation is voluntary and however good practices are recommended to ensure due diligence, transparency and good governance in the RFMS process.

MONITORING, COMPLIANCE AND SANCTIONS

The MR1 of Mauritania suggests two incentives for operators that cooperate with data collection in the form of rewards, first one, suggests increasing quota and second, prioritized access to fishing areas. The auditor questions the sustainability of the first incentive considering the recommendation from CSC to refrain from any increase in fishing effort and catches in this fishery and suggests evaluating the cost-benefit in terms of the stock status compared to data collection to promote such an incentive or thoroughly describe this incentive in case it refers to quota distribution instead of increase. Regarding the second reward, the auditor also questions the sustainability of this incentive if aiming for full participation of the fleet and advises explaining how this incentive can be applicable under full fleet participation in data collection. The auditor advises to consider other incentives other than economic for participation in data collection, such as facilitation of administrative procedures and reporting, privileges in accessing information or reduction of fees and expenses, if applicable.

The MR1 states that not only the operators are responsible for achieving the OTs, the authorities as well as the scientific institution in charge of analysing collected data have additional responsibilities, however there is no mention on how to monitor the compliance of the recommended actions, neither how the scientific activities i.e. molecular sample analysis, required equipment for sample collection and logistics to the scientific institution will be financed and by whom.

The MR1 indicates that FarFish is not position to issue potential sanction or disincentives for lack of cooperation or participation in data collection, however the auditor finds that since participation is

critical for achieving the OTs, it is fundamental to suggest actions that will encourage participation but also discourage abstention and non-compliance.

DOCUMENTATION

The provided documentation is relevant to measure the OTs' indicators; however the auditor considers that this section lacks description in terms of how frequently will the sampling take place and the method for data accessibility, i.e. will the data be kept in a computerized system or in paper form? Also, it is required to clearly state who will oversee the process of collecting and keeping this data and who will cover the costs in the different stages of data collection and analysis to ensure the adequate handling of the data and documentation.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

The MR1 mentioned that obligatory OTs related to black hake fishery were prioritized at this stage through consensus between authorities and operators. Obligatory OTs for small pelagic fisheries and recommended OTs will be reinforced during the 2nd loop. However, there are no OTs related to socioeconomic effects and conditions of the fishery, neither any information to enable an ex ante sensitivity analysis of the potential impacts of the proposed OTs. The auditor recommended baseline data is gathered to know the status of the fishery in order to apply the Audit Framework for RFMS in order to obtain increased likelihood of support to the MR from all relevant stakeholders.

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND RISKS

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address the main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized, and the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MR (MR) relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”.

In general, the risks and strategies to achieving OTs in MR1 are well addressed. However, these strategies and risks are mentioned and suggested for both EU and Non-EU vessels while main goals of MR are only EU fisheries targeting black hake species.

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION

In the MR1 for Mauritania only the obligatory OTs for the black hake fisheries were developed at this stage, therefore the audit framework could only be conducted to OT5.1 and OT5.2 and their indicators, described in Table 36.

Table 36: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets and indicators of CS Mauritania

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries (SFPA), Improved knowledge of fisheries resources (MFMP), Conserve and Sustainable use of the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development (SDG 14)	Improve the quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 5.1 Estimate the proportion of <i>M. polli</i> and <i>M. senegalensis</i> into the catch composition OT Dimension: Ecological	I_1_CS5: Visual identification of subsamples black hake species by vessels targeting black hake
			I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis
			I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake species
		OT 5.2 Collecting data of the black hake bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters OT Dimension: Ecological	I_4_CS5: Training of skippers and crews in visual species identification from subsamples of black hake
			I_5_CS5: Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake
			I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis
			I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake species

In the MR1 for Mauritania it states that the development of MRs and OTs related to the fishery of small pelagic and shrimp requires a differentiated strategy that will be further reinforced during the second loop of the project. The OTs were described in the document for the small pelagic and shrimp fishery, as well as the recommended OTs as described in Table 37. As these OTs were not fully elaborated in the MR1 document, the auditor can only conduct a simple analysis of the OTs statement but cannot fully audit them.

Table 37: Outcome Target mentioned but not elaborated in MR1 for Mauritania

FarFish Outcome Targets for second Loop	Indicator scoring
OT 5.5 Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing for small pelagics in Mauritanian waters where data on landings and catches of all species are reported via electronic reporting (E logbook should include target species, bycatch species and discard where applicable) (Obligatory OT)	Small Pelagic
I OT 5.6 Full on-board observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels (Obligatory OT).	Small pelagic
OT 5.4 Increase knowledge and data collection of all catches in the shrimp fishery, including by-catches. (Recommended OT).	Shrimp Fisheries
OT 5.3: Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing for small pelagics, in Mauritanian waters where data on landings and catches of all species are reported via electronic reporting (E logbook, target, bycatch and discard where applicable) (Recommended OT).	Recommended
OT 5.7: Increase knowledge and data collection of all fleets fishing for small pelagic on trade flows. (Recommended OT).	Recommended

Outcome Targets and Indicators audit

OT5.1. aims to improve the stock assessment of two species of black hake targeted in the Mauritanian fisheries by training operators into visually identify the species onboard (**I_1_CS5**), collect fin samples from visual identification also onboard (**I_2_CS5**) and conduct a molecular analysis of the collected samples in a scientific institution on land (**I_3_CS5**). This OT is directed to the fleet targeting black hake which refers to the vessels from categories 2 and 2bis. Details of the scoring, baseline and responsible are listed in Table 38Table 36.

Table 38: Indicators related to OT 5.1

Outcome Target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 5.1 Estimate the proportion of <i>M. polli</i> and <i>M. senegalensis</i> into the catch composition	I_1_CS5: Visual identification of black hake species by vessels targeting black hake	B	1	Operators
	I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis	C	0	Operators / Authority
	I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake	A	0%	Authority

In general, the auditor considers the described indicators are adequate for measuring the described OTs, however some considerations are provided below:

Indicator **I_1_CS5**, entails the “visual identification of black hake species by vessels targeting black hake”, the identification is expected to be done onboard the vessels, although the operators’ representative OPROMAR manifested some concerns about this process, due to the speed of the fishing operation on board. The auditor questions how this concern has been addressed considering that the responsibility falls on the operator for the performance of indicator **I_1_CS5** according to Table 38. Operator representative OPROMAR to this manifested concern, suggested a supportive visual identification of species on the port after landings since logistics facilitates the visual identification. According to the auditor’s opinion, this supportive visual identification can be conducted by the scientific institution collecting fin samples to be taken according to **I_2_CS5** in coordination with the expected logistic process on port. This task will add an additional verification level from experts in the institution to the visual identification task done by trained skippers and crew on board.

Regarding the scoring of **I_1_CS5**, the auditor questions how this can be measured qualitatively, referring to what amount or proportion of the fish visually identify will render a low, moderate or high level of success, to assign the score. Instead we suggest considering measure this indicator in category A defining a proportion of fish that were successfully identified through visual means and confront the actual samples results or against the suggested supportive visual identification on port, as suggested by OPROMAR. This in our view, will ensure adequate measurement of the indicator and further, enable thorough follow up of the training programs effectiveness. Table 39 summarizes the results from the SMART analysis performed to **I_2_CS5**.

Table 39: SMART Analysis I_1_CS5

Specific	Adequate. Specifically defines the required action
Measurable	It is not clear how the indicator can be measured under category B.
Assignable	Yes, but not all vessels in the relevant categories are yet involved,
Relevant	Partially, supportive visual identification on port suggested by Operator to be considered
Time	Expected frequency of the task is not provided

Following, indicator **I_2_CS5** refers to the “Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis”, this task will also be conducted on board vessel. The auditor considers the success of the sampling process should be measured in both quantitatively and qualitatively (Category A and B), instead of success/failure (Category C) as defined in Table 38. According to this auditor, the description of this indicator allows for the number of samples to be counted and the results of the

sampling to be reported, allowing the indicator to be measured accordingly. This scoring approach allows to follow up of the effectiveness of the training given to the responsible of taking the samples and to identify potential issues that may need attention or additional training.

In addition, the auditor comments that to ensure the success of the sampling task, the two parties responsible for this task should be encouraged to cooperate and properly communicate. Coordination and good communication are needed for collecting the samples and adequate feedback on sample quality and results should be given to skippers and crew by the institution. The auditor suggests defining communication protocols and promoting engagement of parties, joint training sessions or other related activities- between operators and scientific institution. Table 40 summarizes the results from the SMART analysis performed to I_2_CS5.

Table 40: SMART Analysis I_2_CS5

Specific	Yes, clearly describes the required action
Measurable	Number and quality of samples can be quantitatively and qualitatively measured
Assignable	Yes, responsible parties are stated
Relevant	Coordination and communication between parties is needed to ensure relevance to the sampling task
Time	How often and for how long will this task be done is not specified.

Finally, indicator **I_3_CS5** “Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake” this task will be conducted by University of Oviedo, who will coordinate the logistics of the samples from the port to the laboratory. The identified main risks of this task are the ability of the operators to visually identify the two species the results and the adequate handling of the samples, these risks aimed to be reduced through training material and written protocols. The auditor considers that to ensure the success of this task additional communication and feedback from the sampling results should be enabled between the two parties. The suggested joint training sessions and communication channels between operators and scientific institutions are also relevant for the success of **I_3_CS5**. In addition, the scoring of the samples can also be done qualitatively enabling feedback of the number of contaminated or unsuccessful samples, this results feedback will facilitate identifying issues that need to be corrected i.e. additional training, changes in sampling methods or material, etc. The SMART analysis for **I_3_CS5** is described below in Table 41.

Table 41: SMART Analysis I_3_CS5

Specific	Yes, clearly describes the required action
Measurable	Yes, but quality of samples taken can be also measured
Assignable	Yes, responsible party is clearly stated
Relevant	Feedback from sample results to operator can add relevance to task
Time	How often and for how long will this task be done is not specified.

OT5.2 is the second obligatory OT for the black fisheries and refers to “collecting data of the black hake bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters”. OT5.2 is complementary and builds on OT5.1, both serve the purpose of improving the quality of the current stock assessment for the two black hake species fish in Mauritanian waters. This OT aims to measures by four indicators as listed in Table 42. Two of these indicators are shared with OT5.1 namely, I_2_CS5 and I_3_CS5, however in this case the indicators have a broader outreach, aiming to involve all fleets including those not targeting hake in category 3, 6 and 7²⁶. The analysis of the shared indicators I_2_CS5 and I_3_CS5, can be found above in Table 40 and Table 41, however specific notes on the application of the indicators to this OT5.2 are given below.

Table 42: Indicators related to OT 5.2

Outcome Target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 5.2 Collecting data of the black hake bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters	I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis	C	0	Operators / Authority
	I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake	A	0%	Authority
	I_4_CS5: Training of skippers and crews in visual species identification from subsamples of black hake	C	0	Operators/A uthority
	I_5_CS5: Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake as bycatch species	B	0	Operators

In general, the auditor considers the described indicators are adequate for measuring the described OTs, however there is a lack of detailed information on the specific application of the indicators, some considerations are provided below:

I_2_CS5 requires the “collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis” to achieve OT5.2. This indicator aims to reach all the fleet including vessels not targeting hake. This broader outreach adds to the already critical challenge of promoting participation from all relevant operators. An additional challenge is also that these vessels have not conducted hake identification before. The auditor notes that the two suggested approaches to tackle these challenges are to encourage participation of operators in the broader fleet and of the authorities to conduct training activities. However, MR1 does not suggest a tangible strategy, in terms of incentives, onboarding programs or campaigns that can be followed up and measured. The auditor considers that

²⁶ There have been no fisheries in Category 7 in recent years

due to the importance of participation to achieve the goals of OT5.2, there is the need to follow up and measure the participation of operators. Specific indicators can be provided to follow up on level of engagement and participation in sampling programs, such as number of vessels involved, time of involvement in the program, attendees to training programs and other related indicators. The SMART analysis for I_2_CS5, can be found above in Table 40.

I_3_CS5 “Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake” can be found above in Table 41. No additional comments are required for this indicator under OT5.2.

I_4_CS5 refers to “training of skippers and crews in visual species identification from subsamples of black hake”, the auditor questions that this indicator is scored in Category C and considers there will be enough information to score quantitatively in Category A, considering the possibility to provide number of participants to training sessions and compare them to total number of potential participants from all relevant fleets. The SMART analysis for **I_4_CS5** is shown in Table 43.

Table 43: SMART Analysis I_4_CS5

Specific	Yes, clearly describes the required action
Measurable	No mention of frequency of the training programs
Assignable	Yes, responsible parties are clearly stated
Relevant	Yes, lack of knowledge and experience in broader crew
Time	Not stated, when will the training program be carried out and how often

I_5_CS5 refers to the “visual species identification from subsamples of black hake as bycatch species”, however the auditor finds that this indicator is not described in MR1 in length, therefore requires additional information about the difference from this **I_5_CS5** to other indicators referring to visual identification such as **I_2_CS5** and **I_3_CS5**, its applicability and its relevance, to evaluate if there might be overlapping. The SMART analysis elaborates in the mentioned topics as described in Table 44.

Table 44: SMART Analysis I_5_CS5

Specific	No, it is not clear what the purpose of this task is
Measurable	Not clear
Assignable	Yes, responsible party stated
Relevant	Not clear in MR1
Time	Not stated

Since there has not been formulated and OT for socio-economic aspects in the MR1 for Mauritania no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 45Table 33 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 46.

Table 45: Documentation system conformance for Mauritania

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators	CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.	CRITERIA 3. Pilot monitoring programs complement the information control measures.
Outcome Target	Evidence-based for criteria	Evidence-based for criteria	Evidence-based for criteria
Outcome Target for Black Hake Fisheries in Mauritania			
<p>OT 5.1 Estimate the proportion of <i>M. polli</i> and <i>M. senegalensis</i> into the catch composition</p> <p>OT Dimension: Ecological</p>	<p>Due to their morphological resemblance and overlapping occurrence at certain depths, both species are mixed in catches and catch statistics. An improvement of the estimation of the proportion of <i>Merluccius polli</i> (HKB) and <i>Merluccius senegalensis</i> (HKM), will add value to a separated stock assessment</p>	<p>Responsible parties are defined but costs for analysis and training activity are not detailed.</p>	<p>No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>OT 5.2 Collecting data of the black hake bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters</p> <p>OT Dimension: Ecological</p>	<p>Important bycatch of black hake in pelagic fleet. The observer reports are not made available.</p>	<p>The cost of making bycatch data available is not detail in the MR. The auditor assumes that the costs are paid by Authorities</p>	<p>No monitoring programmes were included in the MR</p> <p>N/A</p>
Outcome Target for Small Pelagic Fisheries in Mauritania			
<p>OT 5.5 Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing for small pelagic in Mauritanian waters reported via electronic reporting should include target species, bycatch species and discards</p> <p>Obligatory OT</p>	<p>Check for overlapping with OT 5.3 – Recommended OT</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>Allocation of resources is not detailed in MR1</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>No monitoring programmes were included in the MR1</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>OT 5.6 Full on-board observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels. Obligatory OT</p>	<p>Neither the evidences nor measurement indicators for this OT is detailed in MR1</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>Allocation of resources is not detailed in MR1</p>	<p>N/A</p> <p>No monitoring programmes were included in the MR1</p> <p>N/A</p>

Outcome Target for Shrimp Fisheries in Mauritania						
OT 5.4 Increase knowledge and data collection of all catches in the shrimp fishery, including by-catches. Recommended OT	Neither the evidences nor measurement indicators for this OT is detailed in MR1	N/A	Allocation of resources is not detailed in MR1	N/A	No monitoring programmes were included in the MR1	N/A
Recommended Outcome Target for Mauritania						
OT 5.3: Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing for small pelagic, in Mauritanian waters reported via electronic reporting Recommended OT	Check for overlapping with OT 5.5	N/A	Allocation of resources is not detailed in MR1	N/A	No monitoring programmes were included in the MR1	N/A
OT 5.7: Increase knowledge and data collection of all fleets fishing for small pelagic on trade flows. Recommended OT	Neither the evidences nor measurement indicators for this OT is detailed in MR1	N/A	Allocation of resources is not detailed in MR1	N/A	No monitoring programmes were included in the MR1	N/A

Table 46: Summary of the Evaluation of Management Recommendation for Mauritania

	Phase	Rating	MR1_ Senegal	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3
Step 1 MR Implementation	Documentation system	Risk level	OT1, OT2		N/A	
		Risk level	OT5, OT6	N/A	N/A	N/A
		Risk level	OT4	N/A	N/A	N/A
		Risk level	OT3, OT7	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Alternative MR	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Optimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Pessimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			

3.6 Case Study 6: Seychelles

3.6.1 Documentation System Conformance

The management recommendation (MR1²⁷) for this CS is proposed for the tuna fishery under the Fisheries Partnership Agreement (FPA) between the Seychelles and EU. The EU fleet targeting Yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacares*), Bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*), and Skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) are from Spain, France and Italy. The tuna species in Seychellois waters are managed by the framework of the Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO), The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC), while the Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA) is the executive arm of government for fisheries within the Seychelles EEZ.

As the MR has been delivered to the auditor, this means the document has been approved by the authority, therefore the Auditor assumes that the following questions in Table 47, as defined in the checklist for the operators in the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019a), have been reviewed by the Authority. The table shows a summary of the Auditor’s review for each item on the checklist i.e. whether each item is considered adequately addressed, partly addressed or not sufficiently addressed.

Table 47: Auditor’s review on MR proposal checklist for Seychelles

1.	Have you proposed a management strategy and identified measures that make it clear how you intend to achieve the obligatory OTs mentioned in section 3 of the MR guideline?	Yes
2	Have you identified risks and uncertainties regarding the above-mentioned strategy, and have you explained how it may be adapted?	Partly
3	Have you explained how it will be ensured that individual participants will comply with the measures identified in the plan?	Yes
4	Do you have a strategy for monitoring fisheries activities?	No
5	In case that it is found that some participants do not comply with agreed measures, have you identified sanctions that reflect the severity of likely or foreseeable offences?	Partly
6	Have you described how information will be collected that allows for an audit of whether or not the OTs are achieved? It is clear who will collect each type of data, and is it clear when they should do this?	Yes
7	Have you agreed with the authority on who will serve as auditor, and how its service will be paid?	Yes
8	Is it clear how responsibility will be divided between “authority”, “operators” and “auditor”? Is it clear when each agency should carry out each of their tasks, and is it clear who should cover the costs of this?	Partly
9	Have you explained how the members of your organization(s) have been informed and involved in decision-making regarding the MR development?	No
10	Is it clear how adequate communication between the agencies (“assessors”, “authorities” and “operators”) is ensured?	Yes

²⁷ 1st version MR

According to the auditor's review, in the MR1 for Seychelles the points 2, 5 and 8 are partially covered and points 4 and 9 are not covered in MR1.

AUTHORITIES

MATIS, that acts as the leading authority, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA), the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). The main contact person in this process is Jónas R. Viðarsson²⁸ from WP3, as the leader of Task 3.3.

OPERATOR

The European operator qualified to respond to the MR Invitation for Seychelles are the Long-Distance Advisory Council²⁹ (LDAC), ANFACO-CECOPECA³⁰ and the Organisation of Associated Producers of Large Tuna Freezer Vessels³¹ (OPAGAC). LDAC is an EU fisheries stakeholder led body represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodriguez³². LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs).

MR1 provides clear numbers in terms of the EU fleet accessing fishing opportunities in Seychelles EEZ by gear type and country. The EU fleet is from Spain, France, Italy and Portugal, consisting of tuna seiners and surface long liners. The numbers of national and non-EU vessels are provided in text, without specification of country of the total estimated number. It is recommended to include a table with all the vessels participating in the relevant fisheries.

In addition, it is not clear which vessels will be finally involved in the RFMS. A list with the implicated vessels is recommended to be presented in the MR. Considering the voluntary participation in the RFMS, this table could be updated at the end of the year, if necessary.

Also, from the MR description It is not clear to what extent all vessels of the represented fishing organisation ORPAGAC will accept participating in the MR. Is the assumption that if a fishing association agrees to join in a RFMS' MR, all their members (vessels or skippers) accept the MR?

If not, then each vessel/skipper can choose to be managed under RFMS or not. This fact could cause:

- Increase of management and monitoring cost for operator as well for Authority.
- Lack of trust in the system due to the absence of same level playing field.
- The impact of the MR and its contributions to the overall management objectives would be reduced.

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Finally, in terms of operator it will serve the purpose of this MR to mention potential entering protocol to adhere to the MR from the other relevant operators mentioned, namely ANABAC and ORTHONGEL and the intention to involve them in this process.

MAIN GOAL OF THE MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATION 1 FOR SEYCHELLES

The main goal of MR1 for Seychelles is to enhance the sustainability of the fishery by i) improving the scientific knowledge base for the fisheries management, ii) supporting the fight against IUU fisheries by utilizing the latest available satellite system and tool and iii) enhance a level playing field where all fleets comply by the commitment to honour Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

The main challenges identified in Seychelles Fisheries is the ongoing reorganization of the SFA may affect the MCS of the EU fishing fleet. Other challenges identified mention are the designation of the extended protected marine zones, lack of data for stock assessment of bycatch species, insufficient monitoring and control related to transmission of VMS and AIS data, with the added security issues of Somali piracy. Limited coverage of independent observers and coordination is also mentioned as a challenge for the monitoring and control issue. Other challenges are lack of transparency in agreements with other non-EYU fleets operating in the area and limited knowledge of effects of drifting FADs.

According to this auditor, the challenges identified in the MR are clearly stated and described.

The auditor highlights the need to suggest protocols of interaction with international and local fleet representatives. A clear protocol for adhering and leaving the RFMS and a conflict resolution mechanism can contribute to promoting participation in this MR1.

MR PLANNING PROCESS

The active participation of operators allows FarFish to have a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021). The auditor emphasizes the importance to striving for the participation of all the organizations representing EU vessels actively participating in this fishery to ensure OTs can be fully applicable and achieved. Efforts on finding communication channels with local and non-EU fleet are also relevant.

The planning process section in the document specifies specific time frames and actions associated with the indicators of the OTs described in this MR, the auditor suggest these dates to be included in the OT formulation in order to fulfil the SMART criteria.

This MR does not describe a protocol for other operators to enter the RFMS and how to resolve potential conflicts, in case they emerge, as mentioned above, a concise plan including all previously mentioned factors could to promote participation from the whole fleet in the RFMS and strengthen this MR1. It is acknowledged that participation is voluntary, however good practices are recommended to ensure due diligence, transparency and good governance in the RFMS process.

MONITORING, COMPLIANCE AND SANCTIONS

In general, the MR1 lack descriptions of incentives and sanctions in relation to the OTs. Although the document mention that some management measures are available in IOTC, there is no specific description of which of the measures for control and monitoring are applicable for the purpose of achieving the specified OTs. The auditor suggests to clearly state in the document how these mechanisms can be utilised to strengthen control and monitoring of the OTs. The auditor also considers that MR1 lacks any specific incentives for Operators to collaborate in archiving the identified OTs.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

There are no OT related to socioeconomics and nor are there any information provided to enable an ex ante sensitivity analysis of the impact or consequence of the proposed OTs. This is a recommendation of the Audit Framework for RFMS in order to obtain increased likelihood of support to the MR from all relevant stakeholders.

STRATEGIES; MANAGEMENT AND RISKS

The Audit Framework of the RFMS underlines that management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning “should address main risk and uncertainties that may jeopardize the achievement of obligatory OTs. When such risks and uncertainties are found to be significant, it should be identified how adaptations can be made so that risks are minimized ant the OTs can be met. The main uncertainties to be addressed in the MR (MR) relate to data, implementation of measures and change in environmental conditions”³³.

The auditor considers that the risks to achieving the obligatory OTs described in MR1 are broadly described for OT6.1 and OT 6.6, however this description lacks detail and description on how they can be minimized. No related risks were found for OT6.2. In case the described risks should require following up and mitigation this should be clearly established in specific mention of timing and frequency to conduct controls and follow up the evolution of the factors causing uncertainty i.e. for OT6.1 lack of templates and stakeholder involvement. The auditor finds that the MR1 states that there are mechanisms to be adaptive and facilitate the implementation of the RFMS, although more clarity is needed in the description of the section.

³³. Deliverable 4.4. p. 28

EVALUATION OF THE MANAGEMENT RECCOMENDATION

The obligatory OTs developed in MR1 for Seychelles are described in Table 48, as well as the defined indicators for these OTs.

Table 48: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets and indicators of CS Seychelles

Management goal (CFP (SFP) PGRM, SDG 14, IOTC)	Management objectives	Outcome Target	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries based on the best scientific advice	Improved quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 6.1 Standardization of a fisheries information system (including data provision, handling, processing and analysis) to be used for scientific and research purposes Dimension: Ecological	I_1_CS6: Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the FPA agreement between EU and the Seychelles Indicator score: C
			I_2_CS6: Standardized fisheries information system Indicator score: B
	Improve knowledge base for stock assessment on non-target species currently not assessed due to data limitations	OT 6.2 Development of a protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks Dimension: Ecological	I_3_CS6: Template for catch protocol for non-target species to be implemented in e-logbooks Indicator score: C
Sustainable ecosystem	Protection of Marine Protected Areas	OT 6.6 Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP Dimension: Ecological and Governance	I_6_CS6: Operator compliance Indicator score: C

According to the MR1 document, OT6.1 was rephrased from provision of data to standardization of information system, since it is mentioned that data is provided but dealt with differently depending on the receiver. The auditor considers that this rephrasing makes the OT more specific in accordance of SMART formulation requirement.

Table 49 provides a summary of the indicators, their scoring, baseline and identifies the responsible entities.

Table 49: Indicators related to obligatory OTs in MR1 for CS Seychelles

Outcome Target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 6.1 Standardization of a fisheries information system (including data provision, handling, processing and analysis) to be used for scientific and research purposes Dimension: Ecological	I_1_CS6: Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the FPA agreement between EU and the Seychelles	C	0	Authority, WP2
	I_2_CS6: Standardized fisheries information system	B	0	Authority by IOTC/Operators
OT 6.2 Development of a protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks Dimension: Ecological	I_3_CS6: Template for catch protocol for non-target species to be implemented in e-logbooks	C	0	Authority, WP2
OT 6.6 Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP Dimension: Ecological and Governance	I_6_CS6: Operator compliance	C	n.a	Authority, SFA

The auditor questions why indicator **I_1_CS6** is only measured in category C, since this category does not allow to determine the number of protocols that has been reported for the standardization process and of protocol receivers will adhere to it. It is mentioned that data transmitted is enough for a more detailed follow up of the progress of this task. The auditor suggests exploring other indicators such as the number of formats analysed or standardized in a given period of time from the total number of protocols in place. These indicators allow to provide specific numbers for scoring in category A, strengthening the following up and scoring of this OT. For OT6.1, it is not mentioned if the data receiver organizations have manifest interested in adhering to this standardization initiative. Finally, the OT and its indicators should be formulated SMART as analysed in Table 50:

Table 50: Smart analysis OT6.1

Specific	Is OK, defined specific aim
Measurable	What % of total protocols in place can and will be standardized?
Assignable	Is partly states who is responsible. Lacks description of both ends. Who provided protocols, who adheres to standardized system?
Relevant	What sanctions will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what Nr. of months/years shall the % be obtained?

For OT6.2, the auditor finds that the success of this OT depends on ensuring participation of all relevant operators local, EU and non-EU fleet, there is no mention on how this will be ensured or strived for.

For this OT operators have mentioned that catches of non-target species are recorded when landed, however it also mentioned logistic difficulties to record total catches. Due to this statement the OT6.2 needs clarification in order to determine the actual purpose of this OT and to not create additional effort, if a task is already in place to record non-target species. The auditor suggest that the MR mentions how the operators' comments are considered and how make clear how existing procedure/ protocols can be utilized for the aim of this OT, by improving or modifying them. For this OT it is determinant to ensure that the protocol developed is properly received and applicable for relevant operators.

This leads to the question of if the OT3.4. is formulated SMART as described in Table 51:

Table 51: SMART Analysis OT6.2

Specific	How is this OT adding knowledge if non-target species already recorded? Clarification is needed
Measurable	What % of the fleet will adhere to protocol?
Assignable	Is partly made clear who is responsible.
Relevant	What sanctions will be applied if the assigned does not comply with the measure?
Time	Within what Nr of months/years shall the protocol be adopted/finalized?

Regarding OT6.6 which aims to follow on the Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP with the indicator **I_6_CS6**, the auditor noted following up the success of the indicator depends on the analysis of VMS or AIS data, however it is mentioned above in the document that there are challenges in the VMS data transmission, regarding technical challenges along with different standards in most aspects of the system and there is no national VMS framework in place. These challenges are not addressed in this MR1 also since OT6.5 which aimed to tackle the data transmission challenge was changed from obligatory to recommended. The auditor finds that there are risks and uncertainties that have not been analysed for achieving this indicator as it is described. The auditor recommends to clearly state how the data transmission challenges will be tackled to be able to follow up in the success of this OT or define other indicator that can be used from other more specific data sources i.e. the document mentions management measures that can served this purpose such as the drone system for fighting IUU which can monitor also location of vessels in no-take zones but also the upgrade of the VMS system that is mentioned to be due this year.

The MR1 for Seychelles states recommended OTs listed in Table 52 will not to be addressed in this first version of the MR, but that they are based on important interests and needs reported through stakeholder interaction, both from authorities and operators. MR1 also indicates that strategies to achieve the recommended OTs will be developed in the second version of the MR (MR2). As these OTs were not fully elaborated in the MR1 document cannot fully audit them.

Table 52: Recommended OTs for Seychelles

Recommended Outcome Targets	Responsible
OT 6.3: Setting of conditions for a better coordination of observer programme: content (protocol criteria) schedules, processes, sharing information.	Collaboration Operators and authority
OT 6.4: Provision of data on the use of FADs within Seychelles EEZ. This includes catch data, operating costs and other data relevant for estimating the socio-economic impact of using FADs (particularly drifting FADs)	Not specified
OT 6.5 Transmission of VMS or AIS signals. Dimension: Governance	Not specified

3.6.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Since there has not been formulated and OT for socio-economic aspects in the MR1 for Seychelles no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

To finalize this audit, the documentation system conformance is summarized in Table 53Table 33 and the audit dashboard with the final audit of the MR implementation is provided in Table 54.

Table 53: Documentation system conformance for Seychelles

	CRITERIA 1. The collected data meet with the selected indicators		CRITERIA 2. The resources allocated for the monitoring are available to implement a reliable program.		CRITERIA 3. Pilot monitoring programs complement the information control measures	
Outcome Target	Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria		Evidence-based for criteria	
OT 6.1 Standardization of a fisheries information system (including data provision, handling, processing and analysis) to be used for scientific and research purposes Dimension: Ecological	Sufficient data from existing measures related to the current SFPAs, to SFA and to IOTC. All EU vessels fishing under SFPAs agreement must keep a fishing E-logbook and submit catch data to their flag state by e-logbook		The allocation of resources is not detailed in the MR.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.	n.a.
OT 6.2 Development of a protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks Dimension: Ecological	Bycatch data estimates or observers' reports from all vessels with this data are not provided. Bycatch from EU vessels is recorded during landing and documentation is in place. A protocol will allow assess the status of bycatch species in tuna fisheries		The allocation of resources is not detailed in the MR. Documentation is mentioned but lacks detail in how these documents will be handled and when results should be followed-up		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.	
OT 6.6 Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP Dimension: Ecological and Governance	There is no mention of a clear source of information to follow up compliance of OT6.6. OT6.5 which related to OT6.6. from VMS or AIS data transmission was made recommended, increasing uncertainty in data source.		The allocation of resources for the adaption of management measures is not detailed in the MR.		No monitoring programmes were included in the MR.	n.a.

Table 54: Summary of the Evaluation of Management Recommendation for Seychelles

	Phase	Rating	MR1_ Seychelles	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3
Step 1 MR Implementation	Documentation system	Risk level	OT6.1	●	●	NA
			OT6.2	●	●	NA
			OT6.6	●	●	NA
	Sensitivity analysis	Baseline	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Alternative MR	Lack of data for PCBA			
	Sensitivity analysis	Optimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			
		Pessimistic scenario	Lack of data for PCBA			

4 Final Remarks and Next Steps

The Audit Framework was conducted thoroughly to the six FarFish CS that submitted an approved MR1. Several observations can be drawn from this first audit to build upon the development and continuation of the RFMS process.

Across all cases some challenges were identified by the auditor such as the lack of clear identification of the complete fleet participating in the respective fisheries, as well as a clear framework to involve local and non-EU fleets that states a ways to enter the RFMS and to exit it as well as a protocol for conflict resolution, will strengthen the MRs. Almost all the MRs have defined OTs that aim to increase pressure to all fleets to strive for a level playing-field in the fisheries conducted by multiple fleets in international waters. Therefore, good practice in involving other fleets is fundamental to take most advantage of the RFMS process. This challenge can be tackled in a common manner, finding CS with shared characteristics such as Senegal and Mauritania black hake fisheries, Cape Verde and Seychelles tuna fisheries and the high seas CS.

Another common issue across CS was the lack of specificity in terms of timeline for monitoring and follow up of the management actions, when such were needed. Also, in terms of available resources i.e. human and financial resources, to operationalize the OTs, although these topics were mentioned, they were not specific enough or assigned to specific actions, the auditor suggests to build the documents around the OTs and the indicators performance, to facilitate the audit of the performance of the MR in the second loop.

The MRs displayed a great amount of work and effort from the dialogue and work done by the authority and operators represented in FarFish, however the documents evidence a general lack of data, no CS formulated OT for socio-economic aspects, nevertheless suggested text was provided and the document states the intention to elaborate in these aspects during the second loop. Also, no data has been provided for a sensitivity analysis.

On the other hand, interesting opportunities were also found during the audit that can be utilized to improve and strengthen the MR performance in the second loop. During the audit, it was also found that in some CS i.e. Mauritania and Senegal can benefit from undertaking a more common approach. considering regional strategies, to achieve common goals in shared fisheries in their respective EEZ i.e. Separate stock assessment of the two black hake species targeted in their fisheries and the improvement of the observers' program and capacity.

From these observations the auditor suggests the following steps to be taken to strengthen the MR for the next step of the audit in terms on performance.

- Develop the MR2 around OT and indicators performance be SMART.
- Clearly state relevant fleet in a table with number of vessels from which country, gear type.

- Connect all relevant information inside the different MR section to the relevant OT and indicators performance.
- Clearly define incentives and sanction mechanisms that are applicable to the management goals even if the project cannot enforce them.
- Be specific about resources needed and available funding.
- Establish timetables and follow up on them in document.

The first stage of the audit presented a good overview of the development of MRs in the six different FarFish CS, the RFMS process is running adequately, although timing for completion of tasks was a challenge, the MR showed a great amount of work and dialogue, as well as ambitious but achievable objectives. Common challenges were found such the importance to describe stronger initiative to promote broader participation in the RFMS. Also, interesting opportunities were observed during the audit process such as the possibility to use the capacity building programs to incentivise participation and adherence to the MRs. All together the audit should provide a basis to improve and advance in the developed of the MRs in the next iteration, enabling the operators to improve management goals and implementation strategies, tailoring management strategies to comply with policy requirements while advancing their own objectives and making use of local knowledge and resources. Enabling responsive management with a clear documentation system and audit framework that allow for timely interventions and adaptive management (Nielsen et al., 2018).

Appendix

List of the economic and social fishery indicators

Indicator	Description
Economic indicators	
Addedvalue×revenue ⁻¹ (100a)	Percentage of revenues directed to salary, profit, opportunity cost and depreciation
Gross operative margin × Revenue ⁻¹	Percentage of revenues directed to profit, opportunity cost and depreciation
EBITDA (earnings before interests, tax, depreciation and amortisation)	The EBITDA is essentially net income with interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization added back to it, and can be used to analyse and compare profitability between companies and industries because it eliminates the effects of financing and accounting decisions.
ROS (return on sale)	Percentage of revenues directed to profit, and opportunity cost
ROI (return on investment) (%)	Percent ratio of net profit plus opportunity cost related to investment
Revenue per invested capital (%)	Percent ratio of revenues related to investment
Net profit per vessel (D 000)	Average net profit per vessel
Landings per vessel (tonnes)	Average production (weight of landings) per vessel
Landings per GRT (tonnes)	Average production (weight of landings) per vessel capacity unit (GRT)
Landings per day (tonnes)	Average production (weight of landings) per working day
CPUE (kg)	Average production (weight of landings) per unit effort (GRTa days Number of vessels ⁻¹)
Revenue per vessel (D 000)a	Average production (market value) per vessel
Revenue per GRT (D 000)a	Average production (market value) per vessel capacity unit (GRT)
Revenue per day (D 000)a	Average production (market value) per working day
RPUE (D)a	Average production (market value) per unit effort (GRTa days Number of vessels ⁻¹)
Average price (D kg ⁻¹)	Average market price of landings
Fuel cost per vessel (D 000)	Average fuel cost per vessel
Fuel cost per day (D 000)a	Average fuel cost per working day and vessel
Maintenance cost per vessel (D 000)a	Average maintenance cost per vessel
Social indicators	
Employed persons (num)	Number of men employed person
Landings per crew (tonnes)	Average production (weight of landings) per man employed
Revenue per crew (D)	Average production (market value) per man employed
Crew/GRT	Man employed and GRT employed ratio
Salary per crew (D 000)b	Average salary per man employed person
General sustainability	
Economic sustainability (ESI)	Return on capital invested in fishery – average rate of the Italian Treasury securities with long-term maturity
Social sustainability (SSI)	Average salary per person employed – minimum salary stipulated by the Italian laws

References

- Accadia, P., & Spagnolo, M. (2006). Socio Economic Indicators for the Adriatic Sea demersal Fisheries. In *proceedings of the Thirteenth Biennial Conference of the International Institute of Fisheries Economics and Trade (IIFET)*. Portsmouth.
- Angelsen, A., & Sumaila, U. R. (1995). Hard methods for soft policies. Environmental and social cost-benefit analysis. *CMI Working Paper, WP 1995:1*.
- Caddy, J. F. (2002). Limit reference points, traffic lights, and holistic approaches to fisheries management with minimal stock assessment input. *Fisheries Research*. Elsevier.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-7836\(01\)00343-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-7836(01)00343-5)
- Ceriola, L., Accadia, P., Mannini, P., Massa, F., Milone, N., & Ungaro, N. (2008). A bio-economic indicators suite for the appraisal of the demersal trawl fishery in the Southern Adriatic Sea (Central Mediterranean). *Fisheries Research*, 92(2–3), 255–267.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2008.01.017>
- Cormier, R., Kannen, A., Elliott, M., Hall, P., Davies, I. M., Diedrich, A., ... Andersens, H. C. (2013). *Marine and coastal ecosystem-based risk management handbook*.
<https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.pub.5486>
- EcoFishMan. (2012). *Deliverable 6.2 Methodology for the analysis of factors influencing economics of RFMS*.
- EcoFishMan. (2013a). *Deliverable 4.3 RFMS Prototype 3*.
- EcoFishMan. (2013b). *Deliverable No. 4.4 RFMS Prototype 4*.
- EcoFishMan. (2014). *Deliverable No 6.3 Analysis and evaluation of case studies Revision*.
- FarFish. (2019a). *Deliverable 3.1. 1st Draft General Guidelines for making MRs*.
<https://zenodo.org/record/3073298#.Xe4ww-j7RaQ>
- FarFish. (2019b). Deliverable 3.2. First MR invitations submitted to case studies, 1–68.
<https://zenodo.org/record/3073563#.Xe4w1ej7RaQ>
- FarFish. (2019c). Deliverable 3.4. Description of CS value chains.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3074057>
- Hall, S. J., & Mainprize, B. (2004). Towards ecosystem-based fisheries management. *Fish and Fisheries*, 5(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2960.2004.00133.x>
- ICCAT. (2018). *Report of the Standing Committee on Research and Statistics (SCRS)*. Madrid.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2009). ISO 31000:2009 - Risk management — Principles and guidelines. Retrieved November 26, 2019, from <https://www.iso.org/standard/43170.html>
- Levin, P. S., Fogarty, M. J., Murawski, S. A., & Fluharty, D. (2009, January). Integrated ecosystem assessments: Developing the scientific basis for ecosystem-based management of the ocean. *PLoS Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1000014>
- Nielsen, K. N., Aschan, M. M., Agnarsson, S., Ballesteros, M., Baudron, A., Borges, M. de F., ... Fernandes, P. G. (2018). A framework for results-based management in fisheries. *Fish and Fisheries*.

Fisheries, 19(2), 363–376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12257>

